

Skeletal muscle, cachexia and tuberculosis: a scoping review following the PRISMA-ScR framework

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Abstract

Background

Cachexia, a multifactorial syndrome characterized by skeletal muscle wasting, remains under-studied in tuberculosis (TB), despite TB historically being regarded as the archetypal wasting disease, once termed “consumption”.

Methods

We conducted a scoping review of pulmonary TB (pTB), cachexia, and skeletal muscle, following Arksey and O’Malley’s framework and PRISMA-ScR guidelines. Searches of Medline, Embase, Web of Science, and Africa Journals Online, as well as grey literature, were performed from inception to September 2025.

Results

Of 4,677 records screened, 44 studies met inclusion criteria (42 primary studies, 1 systematic review, 1 narrative review) comprising > 16,500 individuals with TB. Africa was the best-represented region in studies of skeletal muscle followed by Asia; most research was in urban hospital outpatient settings. Most studies were observational and focused on anthropometric of muscle mass, with limited use of gold-standard diagnostic methods. No studies directly defined or measured TB-cachexia. pTB was consistently associated with reduced skeletal muscle mass and function, and low muscle mass at TB diagnosis was associated with increased mortality. Although few studies reported prevalence, skeletal muscle deficits were common when assessed. Muscle mass only partially improves during treatment, remaining below levels observed in healthy controls, with evidence suggesting that weight gain was predominantly due to fat rather than muscle accretion. No studies investigated the short or long-term real-world consequences of musculoskeletal deficits among pTB survivors. Mechanistic studies were scarce, but available data indicated that deficits were more pronounced in men, individuals of low socioeconomic status, and those with severe TB or advanced HIV. Interventions targeting muscle mass and function primarily focused on nutritional or protein supplementation with mixed often transient effects.

Conclusions

Despite frequent reports of wasting in pTB, cachexia has not been clearly defined or phenotyped. Skeletal muscle deficits, central to cachexia, are common in pTB and appear to resolve only partially with treatment, potentially contributing to long-term morbidity. Research is urgently needed to define TB-associated cachexia, elucidating mechanisms of muscle loss, standardize muscle measurement, and evaluate multimodal interventions beyond nutrition to improve survival and recovery.

48 **Background**

49 Tuberculosis (TB), the leading cause of death due to an infectious disease globally, has a complex and
50 multidirectional relationship with nutrition[1]. Weight loss, which can be profound, is a cardinal symptom of TB[2];
51 whilst undernutrition substantially increases an individual's risk of developing TB and thus is an important driver of the
52 ongoing TB epidemic[1].

53 Cachexia is a syndrome involving systemic inflammation, progressive weight and muscle loss, and metabolic
54 derangements that cannot be fully reversed with nutritional support[3, 4]. It has a dramatic impact on survival and
55 quality of life [2, 5-7]. Whilst elements of this syndrome are clearly common among people with TB, most of our
56 understanding of the relationship between TB and nutrition over recent years has been based on crude
57 anthropometric measures of nutritional status, such as body mass index (BMI)[8]. While malnutrition and cachexia
58 overlap, they are not synonymous[3]. Cachexia emphasizes pathological muscle wasting and non-resolution with
59 nutrition, whereas malnutrition does not have the same centring in muscle loss[3, 4, 8-10]. Nonetheless, multiple
60 studies have clearly demonstrated that people with TB who are underweight at the time of TB diagnosis have higher
61 risk of poor outcomes including death compared to those who are not underweight[11, 12]. The RATIONS study found
62 that nutritional supplementation reduced mortality among people with TB, compared to historical data[13, 14].
63 However, importantly they found a subset of people failed to gain weight despite nutritional support, with consequent
64 high mortality[14]. It is highly likely that these individuals had cachexia (which by definition cannot be reversed by
65 nutritional supplementation alone[3]), and that cachexia is important in driving adverse TB outcomes. However,
66 despite TB being one of the archetypal causes of cachexia, the specific syndrome of TB-associated cachexia remains
67 poorly characterized[2]. Furthermore, the contribution of TB as a driver of wasting in people living with HIV- previously
68 referred to as 'Slim disease'[15]) has rarely been investigated.

69 We set out to synthesize the global evidence on TB-related cachexia through a scoping review. Specifically, we
70 sought to understand who develops TB-related cachexia and why[16-18]; the extent to which skeletal muscle mass
71 and function (loss of which are core components of consensus cachexia definitions) recover during and after TB
72 treatment; and the impact of cachexia on long-term functional outcomes and survival[19]. We also sought to highlight
73 opportunities for future research including development of targeted interventions that could improve outcomes from
74 people with TB-related cachexia.

76 **Methods**

77 **Reporting framework**

78 This review was prospectively registered on the Open Science Framework (3 December 2024;
79 <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/7T2EW>[20]). It was guided by Arksey and O'Malley's framework[21] and reported in
80 accordance with the PRISMA-ScR checklist[22].

82 **Study selection**

83 In this scoping review, we sought to gain a broad understanding of the available evidence on TB-related cachexia in
84 the context of adults with pulmonary tuberculosis (pTB). We defined cachexia as: "a multifactorial syndrome of
85 ongoing skeletal muscle loss (with or without fat loss) not fully reversible by conventional nutritional support, leading to
86 progressive functional impairment"[3]. Because this definition requires temporality (i.e., demonstrable *loss* of muscle
87 over time), and our initial scoping search (December 2024) identified few studies explicitly reporting TB-related
88 cachexia, we also included studies that reported relevant muscle measures: specifically, muscle mass and muscle
89 function—without necessarily meeting the full cachexia definition. We refer to these collectively as skeletal muscle
90 deficits and define the key terms and techniques used in this review in Box 1. We excluded studies reporting

91 measures of malnutrition only, i.e., those in which no measures of muscle were reported. We categorised skeletal
92 muscle deficits primarily into a) muscle mass, and b) muscle function (strength, force, and power). We included
93 performance outcomes (6-minute walk test (6MWT)[23], Short Physical Performance Battery (SPPB)[24]) reflecting
94 downstream effects on mobility, lower-limb strength, and balance only when reported alongside measures of muscle
95 mass or function to isolate the effect of skeletal muscle deficits on these aspects of performance.

96
97 TB is commonly categorised as pTB, extrapulmonary TB (EPTB), or disseminated TB; the latter two disease
98 presentations can affect any organ system including the musculoskeletal system. We elected to focus on adults with
99 pTB for this review as we were interested in the multi-system dysfunction and metabolic disturbance related to TB,
100 rather than specific effects through infection of bone or muscle with *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (Mtb) which may be a
101 feature of EPTB. We therefore included studies if the majority (>50%) of participants had microbiologically confirmed
102 pTB. Further, given the changes in musculoskeletal development during childhood and adolescence, we focussed on
103 adults. There was no minimum study sample size. Case reports and studies published in languages other than
104 English were excluded.

105 Our specific review questions aimed to map the literature relating to the epidemiology, mechanisms, economic impact
106 of, and potential interventions for pTB associated cachexia and skeletal muscle deficits. We included studies that
107 reported findings that contributed to any of the domains of evidence (Table 1).

109 **Information sources and search**

110 Our search strategy is described in full in Supplementary Materials (**Supplementary File 1**). We searched Medline
111 (Ovid), Embase, Web of Science Core Collection, and Africa Journals Online from inception to September 3rd, 2025.
112 Grey literature was explored via Google Web using a predefined approach: the first 100 results from three searches
113 were reviewed with relevant articles to be taken through to full text screening. We also searched the WHO website
114 (WHO.int; details in Supplementary Materials).

116 **Selection process**

117 Search results were deduplicated in EndNote and then imported into Covidence (covidence.org; Australia) for further
118 deduplication, screening, and review management. Titles and abstracts were screened independently according to
119 screening eligibility criteria (**Supplementary File 1**) by two reviewers. All titles/abstracts were screened by ADW plus
120 one additional reviewer (EM, CC, KM, DH, MM, or MA). Potentially eligible studies underwent duplicate full-text
121 review, with disagreements resolved through consensus between ADW, CC and EM in fortnightly meetings.
122 Reference lists of included studies were hand-searched for further relevant articles.

124 **Data extraction and synthesis of results:**

125 Data extraction was performed singly using Covidence using a predefined data collection tool. The tool was piloted
126 with 10% of the included studies and, following slight iteration through discussion between reviewers, then used to
127 extract data for all studies. Data were exported to Microsoft Excel and R ((Version 2024.12.1+563)) for processing and
128 analysis.

129 Data were summarised narratively. First, we described the characteristics of included studies, including the distribution
130 by study design, geography, time, and setting. We produced an evidence gap by WHO region across our core review
131 questions. We mapped the evidence available to answer our review questions by these key characteristics to identify
132 evidence gaps, and then narratively summarised the evidence for each of our pre-defined review questions.

134 **Results**

135 The search strategy identified 4677 records after de-duplication, of which 44 were eligible and included in this scoping
136 review (n = 42 primary research studies, 1 systematic review, 1 narrative review) (**Figure 1**). The grey literature
137 search did not yield any additional studies for inclusion. The 42 included primary studies reported on a total of 16,713
138 people with TB. Per-study the number of people included were small to moderate, with a median of 112 individuals
139 with pTB (IQR 47–346). No studies defined, measured or reported on TB-cachexia as defined by any of the
140 standardised consensus (or other) criteria [3, 9, 10], so we focus below on studies that reported on skeletal muscle.
141

142 **Summary of reviews**

143 A systematic review on malnutrition in TB found that the majority of studies 53/69 studies (77%) assessed nutritional
144 status using BMI measurements only, while only 3 of 17 included assessment of muscle (muscle mass mid-arm
145 muscle circumference (MAMC), arm muscle area (AMA), and a composite measure including mid arm muscle
146 circumference (MAMC). The review highlighted a lack of consensus in pTB research on when and how skeletal
147 muscle should be measured and reported[8].

148 The narrative review described the impact of pTB including its association with cachexia, drawing comparisons and
149 insights from the literature on TB-related nutrition and cancer cachexia[2]. It highlighted the complex interplay of
150 nutritional, inflammatory, hormonal, and behavioural factors that contribute to the development of cachexia in general
151 and discussed how these mechanisms may apply in the context of TB.
152

153 **Primary studies**

154 Most primary studies were observational, comprising 22 cross-sectional studies, 12 cohort studies (prospective cohort
155 n = 10, retrospective cohort n =2) and 4 case-control studies. In addition, there were 4 randomized controlled trials.
156

157 *Geographic distribution and publication trends*

158 Africa was the best-represented region in terms of the number of studies related to skeletal muscle (n = 20 studies
159 across 5 countries in Africa), followed by Asia (n = 17 studies across 9 countries). The largest numbers of individual
160 studies from one country were from Tanzania (n = 8) and India (n = 7; **Figure 2A**). No eligible studies were identified
161 from the Eastern Mediterranean region, and only a small number from Europe (n = 3 across 2 countries) and South
162 America (n = 4 across 2 countries).

163 The earliest included studies were published in the 1980s, with the number of publications on this topic per year
164 increasing during the 2000s and peaking during the mid-2010s (**Supplementary Figure 1**).

165 Most studies were conducted in urban or semi-urban settings (n = 34 studies). The majority focused on hospital-based
166 TB clinics and wards (n = 23), outpatient populations (n = 15) and or a combination of both (n = 6). One study did not
167 report the characteristics of the study site.

168 There was variable coverage of review questions in terms of the number of studies and the geographical regions in
169 which studies have taken place (**Figure 2B**). No studies in any regions were identified that reported on TB muscle
170 deficits and their impacts on long term health and social function, on mental health, nor on direct or indirect health
171 costs. No studies investigated the potential for mechanistic pathways to be targeted by interventions.
172

173 **Measurement of pTB associated skeletal muscle deficits in the context of pTB.**

174 42 studies reported measurements of skeletal muscle in people with pTB.
175

176 *Muscle mass*

177 Muscle mass was the most common domain measured (n = 38/42 studies), with most studies estimating muscle mass
178 based on anthropometric measurements (n = 19 measurement entities across n = 18 studies) (**Supplementary**
179 **Figure 2**). These comprised using bedside anthropometric measures such as skin fold thickness, mid-upper arm
180 circumference (MUAC) and height and weight to derive muscle estimates based on equations and references from the
181 1960s and 1970s [25-28]. The muscle estimates described were MAMC (n = 6) and AMC (n = 2), both defined as
182 MUAC - π x triceps skin fold thickness; and arm muscle area (AMA), defined as MAMC squared \div (4 π) (n = 8); and
183 body lean mass, defined using the equations of Durnin and Womersley (n = 3).

184 The second most commonly used method to assess muscle mass was bioelectrical impedance analysis (BIA) (n = 14).
185 Reported BIA outcomes included fat-free mass index, lean mass index, percentage fat-free mass, and body cell mass,
186 which were used as proxies for muscle mass.

187 Less frequently, muscle mass was estimated using dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DXA) (n = 3). Reported
188 outcomes included lean body mass (n = 1), total and limb lean mass (n = 1), and fat-free mass (n = 1). None of the
189 studies reported DXA-derived appendicular lean mass (or its index), which is used as a component of several clinical
190 definitions of sarcopenia in other disease states [29-31].

192 *Muscle function*

193 Muscle function was measured most commonly using handgrip dynamometry to measure handgrip strength (HGS) (n
194 = 13). No studies measured muscle force or power.

196 *Physical performance*

197 Three studies reported on physical performance in association with muscle mass or strength, all of which reported on
198 using the timed chair stand test, which measures the number of times an individual can rise from a seated position to
199 standing and sit back down within ten seconds.

201 **Effects of pTB on muscle mass and function (strength, force, and power), and prevalence of muscle deficits** 202 **among people with pTB**

203 Nineteen studies (1985–2023) from Asia, Africa, and Latin America compared skeletal muscle measurements in
204 people with pTB to comparator groups without TB. Most were cross-sectional (Table 2) at the time of TB diagnosis or
205 during early treatment (N = 14/18 studies); three were longitudinal cohorts (Table 3) whose comparator groups had a
206 single set of measurements whilst the people with TB had repeated measures [32-34]. One study reported measures
207 of muscle mass at the point of completion of TB treatment [35].

208 Comparator groups were heterogeneous, and most commonly comprised community or neighbourhood members (n =
209 8) or “healthy” individuals recruited through health facilities (staff/residents/blood donors/clinic attendees; n = 6) (Table
210 2). Two studies used household contacts or family members. Fewer than half of studies sought to control for
211 confounding through matching: 44% age- and sex-matched, and 39% applied socioeconomic or residential matching.
212 5 studies applied adjustment to control for confounding in analyses. Three studies included HIV-positive and TB-
213 negative comparators recruited from cohorts involved in other studies, or from HIV clinics. TB-negative status of
214 controls was explicitly confirmed in 3/19 studies. One study did not report control selection.

215 Across the included studies, people with pTB before or at the start of treatment consistently had with lower skeletal
216 muscle mass and function and physical performance than comparators, with variation in the magnitude of difference
217 by study design, adjustment for confounding, and population (Table 2). For measures of mass, arm muscle area
218 (AMA) and arm muscle circumference were lower in people with TB (mean difference 13–29 cm² [n = 4] and 3 cm [n =
219 1] respectively), as were anthropometry-derived total lean mass (mean difference 15 kg; n = 1), free fat mass (mean

220 difference 4.4 kg (men) and 4.8 kg (women); n = 1; clinically detectable muscle wasting (46-56% of PWTB vs 0%
221 controls; n = 1) and low MAMC (48.6% of PWTB vs 25.7% controls; p=0.04; n = 1). Bioimpedance findings were
222 directionally consistent: body cell mass was lower by 0.1–3.3 kg (n = 3) and lean mass index (LMI) was lower by 1.7
223 kg/m² in men and 1.2 kg/m² in women (n = 1). The single DXA study reported approximately 6.0 kg (approximately
224 13%) less lean mass in people with TB. For muscle function, handgrip strength was lower by 6.8–18.0 kg (n = 5). Only
225 one study assessed performance, reporting 25% fewer chair-stands in 10s among people with TB. In the one study
226 assessing muscle mass at TB treatment completion, there was no difference between people with TB and
227 comparators.

228 Among studies which reported the proportion of people with skeletal muscle deficits below a defined threshold, seven
229 reported the prevalence of low muscle mass before or at the time of TB diagnosis, while one study reported post-
230 mortem prevalence of “skeletal wasting” [39]. No studies reported the prevalence of low muscle strength, power, or
231 physical performance.

232 Prevalence of muscle deficits varied between 25.9 to 91% based on measurement method (**Table 2 and 3**). Using
233 the most common method of measuring muscle deficit prevalence (MAMC below study-specific thresholds; n = 4),
234 prevalence varied between 48.6 and 91%. BIA was used in two studies to define LMI using recognised cut-offs (men
235 <16.7 kg/m²; women <14.6 kg/m²); reporting prevalence of low lean mass among 14-50% of people with TB. One
236 study used CT-derived T12 skeletal muscle index (SMI) to identify 12-22% PWTB as having low muscle mass. There
237 were no clear trends in the prevalence of muscle deficits across world regions, with comparisons limited by the small
238 number of studies and heterogeneity in definitions. This highest reported prevalence (based on MAMC) was from
239 Brazil[36] and the lowest (based on SMI) was from China[37].

241 **Trajectories of pulmonary TB cachexia prior to TB diagnosis, during treatment and during recovery**

242 We identified 12 studies which evaluated skeletal muscle longitudinally during TB treatment (Table 3) including two
243 that extended follow-up beyond treatment completion. Five studies assessed muscle mass using anthropometric
244 measures [38] [32] [39] [33, 40], three used BIA [41-43], and two applied deuterium dilution to estimate changes in
245 body composition over time [44, 45]. Five studies evaluated handgrip strength as a measure of muscle function and
246 one assessed physical performance using the Chair Stand Time.[34, 38-40, 46].

247 Overall, muscle mass recovery varied across individuals and settings, with most studies reporting stable or modest
248 improvement over time. Studies using BIA and deuterium dilution – considered more robust methods of measuring
249 body composition - generally found limited muscle recovery despite increases in weight and BMI (**Figure 3; Table 2**).
250 In two studies very limited to no further muscle recovery was observed beyond the first 6 months of TB treatment.[32,
251 43] All studies measuring handgrip strength reported improvement over time, as did the single study assessing
252 physical performance, although the latter did not include a statistical test of significance.

Impact of pulmonary TB cachexia on TB treatment outcomes

Six cohort studies (four retrospective, [43, 47, 48] two prospective[18, 41]) examined association between skeletal muscle mass or function and TB outcomes, primarily mortality (Table 4). Four studies focused on inpatients.

Retrospective studies used radiological or bioimpedance-derived mass estimates, while prospective cohorts assessed handgrip strength, mobility and serial BIA. Across studies lower skeletal muscle mass was consistently associated with higher mortality risk with effect sizes ranging from a 2-fold [43, 48] to over 20-fold increase[37]. Associations persisted after adjustment for TB severity markers (e.g. BMI, CRP) with no clear difference by HIV status.

One study reported on the different trajectories of muscle mass in those who subsequently survived compared to those who died during TB treatment, finding that TB survivors gained muscle mass whilst those who die lost muscle mass prior to death [41].

Potential biological mechanisms underlying muscle deficits in pTB

Mechanistic studies

Macallan et al used leucine kinetics to investigate whole body energy and protein metabolism in nine individuals with pTB compared with six undernourished participants and six people with malnutrition healthy controls[49]. People with TB, showed a reduced ability to utilise ingested amino acids for protein synthesis in response to an anabolic stimulus suggesting that TB-associated cachexia impairs the formation of muscle and other tissues following nutritional intake.

Factors associated with skeletal muscle deficits

Twenty-six studies examined factors associated with muscle deficits at TB diagnosis or with muscle recovery during treatment (summarised in Supplementary Table 1; full details of studies in Supplementary Table 2. Five studies assessed muscle function, while the remainder focused on mass. Few associations were consistent across studies, but several potential risk factors for low muscle mass mirrored those linked to delayed presentation or severe TB disease including male sex, smoking, HIV infection and low socioeconomic status (Supplementary tables 1 and 2). Two studies suggested effect modification by sex, with lower muscle mass observed among men but not women living with HIV. As expected, markers of disease severity (e.g. radiographic extent, drug resistance) were often associated with reduced skeletal muscle mass and more extensive disease was associated with lower grip strength. Across eight studies assessing recovery trajectories, one reported a trend towards reduced muscle mass recovery among current smokers after adjustment for confounders ($p=0.08$). No consistent associations were found with socio-economic position, diet, diabetes, HIV status and CD4 count.

Interventions for management of TB cachexia

We identified four intervention trials that reported skeletal muscle outcomes (Table 5). All were randomized controlled trials of nutritional supplementation (4 with micronutrient supplementation; 2 studies with protein enrichment) during TB treatment with and without dietary counselling. These demonstrated modest short-term improvements in weight gain and grip strength, but limited evidence of consistent or sustained benefits in lean mass or muscle function (Table 5).

Discussion

In this scoping review we set out to synthesize the global evidence on cachexia among people with pTB and to identify gaps to inform a research agenda.

300 Overall, despite weight loss and cachexia being archetypal features of TB[50], we identified only 44 studies which
301 reported measures of muscle mass or function among people with pTB and very limited or no evidence across some
302 of our review questions. These were, on the whole, small studies that spanned a wide time period and geographic
303 regions, limiting the robustness of our conclusions. Notably no studies used a consensus definition of cachexia[3]; our
304 findings are therefore based on skeletal muscle measures as a proxy of cachexia[8]. Across included studies, skeletal
305 muscle deficits were common in pTB, with more severe muscle loss associated with severe TB disease and higher
306 mortality. Underweight (defined by BMI) and low body fat were also common: it remains to be determined if TB-related
307 cachexia is a distinct entity to malnutrition among people with pTB and how muscle deficits, above and beyond low
308 total body mass, impact short and long-term survival.

309
310 Importantly, the current data suggests that muscle mass recovery among people with pTB is incomplete, with limited
311 evidence that nutritional interventions impact muscle specific measures. Whilst lack of muscle recovery may contribute
312 to long-term post-TB disability and mortality, the lack of long-term follow up means this is unknown. Sarcopenia, which
313 characterized by progressive loss of skeletal muscle mass and/or strength is prevalent in regions including Africa with
314 high TB prevalence[Zengin, 2018 #4058]. To date the relationship between pTB and clinical diagnosis of sarcopenia
315 has not been explored. Improved understanding of this relationship will be crucial given the established relationship
316 between sarcopenia, morbidity and mortality[Zengin, 2018 #4058], it will be important to determine whether TB leads
317 to increased rates of sarcopenia in the short and long term.

318
319 Socio-economic deprivation appeared to be associated with greater muscle deficits at TB diagnosis. This may reflect
320 pre-existing protein malnutrition and lack of access to care resulting in more severe disease at presentation. In the
321 context of renewed interest in nutritional interventions as a strategy to prevent TB and improve outcomes, there is an
322 urgent need for further, high quality research to understand the mechanisms of TB-related cachexia and how these
323 may be ameliorated through interventions (Box). First, to catalyse interest and enable meaningful comparison across
324 studies, an adapted operational definition of TB-related cachexia is needed. The current consensus definitions of
325 cachexia is specific to cancer and requires demonstration of longitudinal evidence of weight loss[4, 9], which more
326 conceptual definitions require an element of non-responsiveness to nutritional support [51]. Given most people with
327 TB are identified, and recruited into research studies, at the time of their diagnosis, prior weight is rarely known
328 (particularly in low and middle income countries without electronic health records, where most people with TB live),
329 self-reported weight loss is insensitive[1], and nutritional response may be difficult to accurately capture: these
330 requirements may need to be relaxed in an operational definition of cachexia to be used in TB research.

331
332 Secondly, research to date has used a range of methods and thresholds to measure and define low muscle mass or
333 function among people with pTB. Often these are crude, historic methods based on extrapolation from anthropometric
334 indices (such as MAMC, AMC), with very few studies using modern, gold standard methods of body composition and
335 muscle mass estimation such as DXA and dilution methods. The anthropometric measures used have not been
336 validated among people with TB and we note reference datasets were all from HIC, mainly the USA[52], emphasizing
337 the importance for reference datasets in high-TB burden settings. Whilst we also recognise that access to more
338 advanced methods may be limited in some high-TB burden settings, their implementation is feasible, as we have
339 demonstrated in Zimbabwe, the Gambia and South Africa[53]. To support research into the role of cachexia in people
340 with TB more broadly, we suggest validation of low-cost, rapid, portable assessments of muscle mass and function
341 (e.g. AMA and grip strength) against reference standard methods (e.g. DXA derived indices and jump-plate
342 mechanography) among people with TB, to support their broad use in TB research studies. Sarcopenia,

343
344 Third, the heterogeneity and limited number of studies included in this review means the true prevalence of TB-related
345 cachexia is unknown. Epidemiological research including prospective cohort studies with long-term follow up is
346 needed to understand the prevalence of cachexia among people with TB across populations, the intersection of
347 cachexia and underweight, the role of nutritional composition in development of and resolution from TB-related
348 cachexia, risk factors for cachexia, and the impact of cachexia on short- and long-term clinical and patient-important
349 outcomes. This should specifically consider cachexia among people with key comorbidities, including HIV, silicosis, or
350 diabetes. Ideally, this would include cohort studies among people at risk of TB, to understand the extent to which
351 muscle deficits are caused by TB, as opposed to being pre-existing, perhaps even having a role in increasing risk of
352 developing TB.

353 Given the association between muscle deficits and increased mortality identified in this review, clinic-based
354 measurement of muscle mass or grip strength could add value as triage tools in clinical management of TB, identifying
355 people at increased risk of morbidity and mortality and prioritising them for additional monitoring or tailored
356 interventions; this as yet remains unexplored and thus it is not known what such measures might add over currently-
357 recommended measurement of weight at TB diagnosis, and monitoring during treatment.

358 Fourth, whilst it is well recognised that muscle weakness limits functional capacity and ability to work[54] no studies to
359 date have explored the socio-economic impacts of muscle deficits among people with tuberculosis. It is plausible that
360 muscle deficits during and post-TB are a key mechanism driving poorer physical function[55] and lack of economic
361 recovery[56]. Thus TB-related cachexia could be a further compounding factor in tuberculosis syndemics[57].
362

363
364 Fifth, we found only one study investigating the mechanisms driving muscle loss in pTB[49]. Emerging evidence from
365 cancer cachexia reveals cachexia to be a complex interplay between systemic inflammation, catabolism, behavioural
366 factors (e.g. anorexia, depression, withdrawal) and muscle wasting[5-7, 58, 59] Whether these mechanisms also drive
367 TB-cachexia is unknown, but warrants exploration through discovery research, supporting translation of promising
368 therapies for cancer cachexia to host-directed therapies for TB.
369

370 In studies which evaluated both muscle and fat compartments, increases in fat appeared to be the major contributor to
371 weight gain during TB treatment. It is possible that TB-related weight loss is mostly fat loss. This urgently warrants
372 further interrogation, particularly in light of emerging evidence of increased cardiovascular risk among TB survivors –
373 risks that may be increased by rapid increases in fat deposition – to ensure that the current push for nutritional
374 intervention in pTB includes optimization to promote healthy recovery in weight[60].
375

376 Finally, there is extremely limited data on interventions which could improve recovery of muscle mass and function,
377 promoting post-TB physical performance and wellbeing. The data that do exist are limited to small studies of
378 nutritional interventions. Notably, there is increasing interest in pulmonary rehabilitation during or after TB to improve
379 post-TB functional capacity; with evidence for improvement in 6-minute walk test with this intervention. These studies
380 were not included in this review as none measured muscle indices. Understanding the TB-cachexia in the context of
381 rehabilitation would support optimisation of this intervention.
382

383 Strengths of this review include a comprehensive search strategy across multiple databases, including grey literature;
384 limited exclusion criteria; a predefined protocol; and double data extraction. However, we excluded studies published
385 in languages other than English, which may have introduced geographical bias and contributed to the under-

386 representation of studies from South America, West Africa, and Central Asia. Additionally, we included only studies
387 with a majority of microbiologically confirmed pulmonary TB cases. While this approach increased the certainty of TB
388 diagnosis, it may have excluded studies with more heterogeneous and 'real-world' cohorts, potentially limiting
389 generalizability.

392 **Conclusion**

393 Skeletal muscle deficits are common in adults with pTB, yet TB-cachexia has not been directly defined or measured in
394 primary literature. Most evidence relies on low-cost measures of muscle mass, with limited use of gold-standard or
395 validated methods and limited data on muscle function or power. Low muscle mass at diagnosis predicts higher
396 mortality; however, recovery during treatment is variable and often incomplete, and long-term musculoskeletal and
397 functional outcomes remain largely unknown. Mechanistic evidence is minimal, with associations suggesting those
398 with severe TB, advanced HIV and living in difficult socioeconomic circumstances may be at higher risk of muscle
399 deficits and potentially therefore cachexia. Interventional studies have focused mainly on nutrition, and whilst protein
400 supplementation appears to show promise, overall results were mixed. Defining and formally measuring TB-cachexia,
401 standardising skeletal muscle measurement, and evaluating multimodal interventions (nutrition, exercise, and
402 pharmacological or metabolic strategies) in high-burden settings are priorities to improve survival and recovery.

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Box 1 Key terms & operational definitions (used in this review)

Skeletal muscle deficits

Presence of abnormal muscle mass and/or reduced muscle function or performance, irrespective of documented longitudinal loss.

Muscle mass

Objective measures of muscle size or composition. Examples include anthropometric measurement-based estimates such as mid-arm muscle circumference, calculated by adjusting mid-arm muscle circumference by the amount of subcutaneous fat (measured using skin fold thickness; formula: $MAMC = MUAC - \pi \times TSF$). Other methods of measuring muscle mass include DXA (dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry) appendicular lean mass (ALM, $ALM/height^2$), CT or MRI cross-sectional area or muscle attenuation, bioimpedance-derived fat-free mass, ultrasound thickness.

Muscle function (strength/force/power):

Maximal voluntary force or power generation by specific muscle groups. Examples include measures of strength: Handgrip strength, knee extensor strength (isometric/isokinetic); and force and power: jump plate mechanography.

Physical performance (mobility/functional capacity):

Whole-body tasks integrating multiple systems. E.g. Gait speed (4–10 m), Short Physical Performance Battery (SPPB), 6-Minute Walk Test (6MWT), Timed Up and Go (TUG), Chair Stands Time (number of stands for seated position completed in 10 seconds).

Key measurement modalities (for this review)

Anthropometry:

Tape and caliper measures (e.g., MUAC, triceps skinfold, $MAMC = MUAC - \pi \times TSF$, calf circumference, AMA) providing low-cost proxies of muscle bulk; operator skill and edema/fat distribution limit accuracy.

Bioelectrical Impedance Analysis (BIA):

Passes a low-level alternating electrical current between electrodes placed on the body; measures resistance, and reactance to estimate body composition including total body water (TBW), fat-free mass (FFM) and fat mass (FM); common outputs include phase angle and body cell mass (BCM); sensitive to hydration status and the prediction equation/device.

Dual-energy X-ray Absorptiometry (DXA):

Uses two X-ray photon energies with tissue-specific attenuation to partition bone mineral, fat mass, and lean soft tissue; key outputs include appendicular lean mass (ALM) and $ALM/height^2$ for sarcopenia classification; low radiation dose, high precision, but device/software specific.

Dilution methods:

Isotope dilution (e.g., D_2O for TBW, bromide for extracellular water) to quantify body water compartments; derive $FFM = TBW/0.73$ and $FM = \text{body mass} - FFM$; reference techniques but cost/logistics intensive.

Handgrip strength (HGS):

Calibrated dynamometry (maximal isometric trials; best or mean recorded) indexing upper-limb strength; quick, inexpensive, widely standardized.

Abbreviations and related terms

6MWT — 6-Minute Walk Test.

AMA — Arm Muscle Area (from MUAC and triceps skinfold).

ALM — Appendicular Lean Mass from DXA; $ALM/height^2$ used in sarcopenia classification.

BCM — Body Cell Mass (BIA-derived, metabolically active FFM component).

BMI — Body Mass Index ($kg \cdot m^{-2}$).

CT — Computed Tomography

DXA — Dual-energy X-ray Absorptiometry (bone, fat, lean; source of ALM).

FFM / LM — Fat-Free Mass / Lean Mass (kg).

FFMI / LMI — Fat-Free (Lean) Mass Index ($kg \cdot m^{-2}$).

HGS — Handgrip Strength (maximal isometric).

MAMC — Mid-Arm Muscle Circumference = $MUAC - \pi \times TSF$.

Mechanography — Force-plate assessment of lower-limb force/power.

MRI — Magnetic Resonance Imaging (muscle volume/composition; no ionizing radiation).

MUAC — Mid-Upper Arm Circumference.

SPPB — Short Physical Performance Battery (0–12 composite).

Box 2: Key research priorities**Consensus definition**

Develop a TB-relevant consensus definition of cachexia/skeletal muscle deficits, including standardized thresholds for mass, strength, and performance.

Validate low-cost measures

Validate pragmatic/low-cost assessments (e.g., MUAC/MAMC/calf circumference, BIA/phase angle, handgrip, simple performance tests) against gold-standard measures (DXA, dilution methods, isokinetic dynamometry, mechanography) in people with TB.

Prevalence and comparisons

Develop appropriate reference standards for muscle measurements in high TB burden settings, allowing the measurements of the prevalence and severity of cachexia among people with tuberculosis across world regions using harmonized methods.

Long-term outcomes and economics

Conduct longitudinal follow-up to characterize trajectories of muscle mass, strength, and performance post TB treatment; evaluate impacts on clinical outcomes, quality of life and health economics; routinely include muscle-specific measures in post-TB studies.

Mechanistic studies

Elucidate biological drivers (inflammation, endocrine and appetite signaling, myosteatorsis, mitochondrial function) and interactions with HIV, diabetes, and the microbiome.

Interventions and trials

Develop and test multimodal interventions (nutrition, anti-inflammatory/anabolic pharmacotherapy, exercise/rehabilitation), with implementation research for scalability in low-resource settings.

FOZ

Figure 1. PRISMA 2020 Flow Diagram of Study Selection

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Footnotes: n = number

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Figure 3: Muscle Mass and Functional Recovery during pTB treatment by method of assessment

Grey panels represent when no studies have addressed the review question in a particular WHO region. *All studies represented in Americas region were from South Africa (none from North America)

Footnotes: For

Praygod (2015) and Jahnvi (2010), the mean value at follow up was estimated from the reported baseline and change from baseline. Dashed lines indicate the mean for healthy controls, in studies for which this data was available (indicated by colour). **Abbreviations:** **%PM:** percent protein mass, estimated from **deuterium oxide (²H₂O) dilution: protein mass** is the non-water, non-mineral component of fat-free mass and is reported as % of body mass. **AMA:** arm muscle area (cm²); **AMC:** arm muscle circumference (cm); **FFM:** fat-free mass (kg); **LMI:** lean mass index (kg/m²); **HGS:** handgrip strength (kg); **Chair stands/10 s:** number of chair-stands completed in 10 seconds (N).

Table 1. PCC Framework defining the eligibility criteria and research questions for this scoping review.

Domain	Population	Concept	Context
Epidemiology	People with pTB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measurement of cachexia and skeletal muscle deficits (RQ1). • Effects of pTB on muscle mass, function (strength, force, power), physical performance, activities of daily living (RQ2a). • Prevalence of cachexia/muscle deficits at diagnosis, during, and after treatment among people with TB and in comparison with healthy people without TB(RQ2b). • Natural history before diagnosis, during treatment, and recovery (RQ2c). • Associations with TB outcomes (RQ3). • Long-term health and social consequences (education, employment, productivity, relationships) (RQ4). • Effects on mental health before, during, and after treatment (RQ5). 	Any healthcare or community setting where people with pTB are assessed, treated, or followed up.
Mechanisms	People with pTB (human studies ± relevant preclinical/ animal work if included)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biological mechanisms underpinning cachexia and muscle deficits (inflammation, hormonal, metabolic, nutritional, mitochondrial, etc.) (RQ6). • Mechanisms potentially amenable to intervention (RQ7) 	Clinical, laboratory, or experimental settings.
Economics	People with pTB (and households/ health systems)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct and indirect health costs (including out-of-pocket), productivity losses, healthcare utilization, economic burden (RQ8) 	Health system, household, and societal contexts.
Interventions	People with pTB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nutritional, pharmacological, exercise/rehabilitation, or multimodal interventions (RQ9) 	Clinical trials, observational studies, or programmatic interventions in any setting.

Footnotes: pTB = pulmonary TB; RQ = research question.

543 Table 2: Cross sectional studies reporting muscle deficits in pulmonary TB (with and without comparator groups without pTB)

Measurement	Author (year)	Country & setting	Period of recruitment	PWTB	Control	Measurement	Outcome: N		Statistical test	Adjustment
							PWTB	Control		
Assessments of muscle mass using clinical assessment and anthropometric measures										
<i>Before/at start of treatment</i>										
Clinical assessment	Metcalfe (2005)[61]	Sri Lanka, urban, outpatients	2002	Smear+ pTB; known HIV+ excluded. Mean age: 50.1 Men: 60% PLHIV: exclusion if known	Air Force staff and health lecture attendees. Unmatched. Mean age: 39.1 Men: 60% PLHIV: exclusion if known	% Temporal shoulder wasting (CI) % Deltoid shoulder wasting (CI)	56% (42-70); N = 50 46% (32-60); N = 50	0%; N = 49 0%; N = 49	χ^2 test, p<0.05 χ^2 test, p<0.05	Unadjusted
Lean body mass (LBM)	Macallan (1998)[49]	India, urban, Inpatients and outpatients	Unknown	Mainly smear+ pTB Mean age 43.2 Men: 77.8% PLHIV: unknown%	Recruited from local population, BMI >20kg/m2. Unmatched. Mean age 28.4 Men: 85.7% PLHIV: unknown%	Mean total LBM in kg (SD)	41.9 (2.5); N = 9	50.9 (6.1); N = 7	Fisher's PLSD test, p<0.05	Unadjusted
Fat-free mass (FFM)	Karyadi (2000)[62]	Indonesia, urban, outpatients	Unknown	Smear+ pTB (100%) Mean age 28.0 (across both TB and controls, not reported separately) Men: 61.0% PLHIV: unknown% (not tested)	Neighbours of PWTB. Matched for age and sex. Men: 61.0% PLHIV: unknown%	Mean FFM in kg (SD) – Men Mean FFM in kg (SD) – Women	43.3 (5.6); N = 25 31.2 (3.8); N = 16	47.8 (4.4); N = 25 36.0(5.2); N = 16	T test, p<0.05 T test, p<0.05	Unadjusted
Mid arm muscle circumference (MAMC)	Da Silva (2019)[36]	Brazil, urban Unknown clinical setting	2017-2018	Mainly smear+ pTB Mean age: 37.5 Men: 69% PLHIV: 40%	Family members of PWTB. Matched by age and sex. Mean age: 38.6 Men: 69% PLHIV: 9%	% Malnutrition by MAMC (n/N) Reference comparator/cut off not stated	49% (17/35)	26% (9/35)	χ^2 test, p=0.04	Unadjusted
	Lazzari (2018)[63]	Brazil, urban, inpatients	Unknown (ethical approval 2002)	Adults hospitalized mainly smear+ (68.5%) pTB. Mean age: 44.9 Men: 71% PLHIV: 41%	None	% Malnutrition by MAMC (n/N) MAMC cut off vs ref standards [64]	59.3% (64/118)	No comparator group without TB	NA	NA
	Moraes (2014)[33]	Brazil, urban		pTB Mean age 38.4 Men: 100% PLHIV exclusion	None	% Muscle mass depletion (n/N) MAMC cut off vs ref standards [52]	91% (31/35)	No comparator group without TB	NA	NA
	Nkhoma (1987)[65]	Malawi, Nigeria, urban inpatients	Unknown	Smear+ pTB (87% Mean age 35.0 Men: 100% PLHIV exclusion	None	Mean MAMC in cm (SD) – Men, Malawi Mean MAMC in cm (SD) – Women, Malawi Mean MAMC in cm (SD) – Men, Nigeria Mean MAMC in cm (SD) – Women, Nigeria	20.4(2.5) 19.1(2.2) 19.9(2.8) 18.4(2.7)	No comparator group without TB	NA	NA

Arm Muscle Area (AMA)	Range (2010)[66]	Tanzania, in-and outpatients	2001-2002	Smear+pTB (100%) Mean age: 35.3 Men: 56.4% PLHIV: 44%	Randomly selected community controls No matching reported. Mean age: 33.0 Men: 51% PLHIV: 11%	Mean AMA in cm2 – Men Mean AMA in cm2 – Women	35.7; N = 314 31.7; N = 218	53.2; N = 76 44.9; N = 74	Linear regression: Difference (PTB vs non-TB) (95% CI) M = -17.5 (-20.0–15.0); P < 0.001 F = -13.2 (-15.4–11.0); P<0.001	Difference remained in both men and women after adjustment for age, height, and HIV
	Praygod (2011)[67]	Tanzania, urban; outpatient clinics	2006-2009	Smear+ pTB (100%) Mean age: 34.2 Men: 75.7% PLHIV: 47%	Randomly selected, community controls. Age and sex matched. Mean age: 33.9 Men: 75.7% PLHIV% 10%	Mean Arm muscle area in cm2 – Men Mean Arm muscle area in cm2 – Women	34.8; N = 193 32.4; N = 162	36.5; N = 193 46.0; N = 162	Multivariable analyses (mean diff) M = -3.4, P=0.03 F = -12.1 P<0.001	Adjusted for age, HIV
	Harries (1985)[68]	Nigeria, rural, inpatients	1984	Mainly smear+(73%) pTB Mean age: 29 Men: 62% PLHIV: unknown%	Hospital staff. Age, and sex matched. Mean age: unknown Men: unknown % PLHIV: unknown%	Mean AMA in cm2 (SD) – Men Mean AMA in cm2 (SD) – Women AMA < 5 th centile (compared to reference[52]): %(n/N)	32.0 (8.7); N = 54 27.5 (7.9); N = 32 75% (63/86)	47.7(7.7); N = 54 39.0(11.4); N = 32 31%;(21/86)	T test p<0.001 T test p<0.001 χ ² test P<0.001	Unadjusted
Other/unknown timing										
Clinical assessment (postmortem) for presence of cadaveric skeletal wasting	Lucas (1994)[15]	Ivory Coast, urban, mortuary	1999	People who died with HIV (inpatients) TB confirmed by histopathology Mean age: unknown Men: unknown% PLHIV: 100% Median CD4: 47 in wasted group	People who died with HIV, no evidence of TB. Unmatched. Mean age: unknown Men: unknown% PLHIV: 100% Median CD4: 44 in wasted group	% with evidence of skeletal wasting (n/N)	52.5% (42/80)	40.2% (53/132)	Nil	NA
Lean body mass (LBM) (unknown timing)	Sharma (2008)[69]	India, urban, inpatients and outpatients	Unknown	Confirmed pulmonary TB. Diagnosis method unknown Mean age: 35.2 Men: 100% PLHIV: unknown	Recruited from “same place.” Matched for age, sex, and socioeconomic status. Mean age: 37.2 Men: 100% PLHIV: unknown	Mean LBM in Kg (SD)) – Overall	38.1 (5.0); N = 86	53.5 (8.1); N = 40	T test p<0.05	Unadjusted
Total body cell mass (BCM) Unknown timing of assessment	Niyongabo (1994)[70]	Burundi, urban, inpatients	1993	Smear+ pTB (100%) Mean age: 33.4 Men: 86% PLHIV: 84%	None	Mean BCM in kg (SD) – TB+ PLHIV Mean BCM in kg (SD) – TB+HIV-	36.3 (4.0) 40.3 (4.3)	No comparator group without TB	NA	NA
Assessments of muscle mass using dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry										
<i>Before/at start of treatment</i>										

Lean body mass (LBM) (DXA)	Paton (2006)[71]	Singapore, urban, outpatients	1999-2000	Men with culture confirmed pTB and wasting (BMI<20 kg/m ²) Mean age 38.6 Men: 100% PLHIV: 56%	Hospital staff, blood donors Mean age 39.3 Men: 100% PLHIV: 50% Hep B carriers 15%	LBM in kg (SD) Total limb lean mass in kg (SD)	39.6 (4.5); N = 18 15.2 (2.3)– N = 18	45.6 (4.3); N = 22 19.1(1.9); N = 22	T test p<0.001 T test p<0.001	Unadjusted
Assessment of muscle mass using bioimpedance analysis (BIA)										
<i>Before/at start of treatment</i>										
Body cell mass (BCM), Kg (BIA)	Mupere (2010)[72]	Uganda, urban, outpatient clinics	2002-2008	Smear+pTB (100%) Mean age: 30.0 Men: 53.5% PLHIV: 44%	Household contacts. No matching reported. Mean age: 30.3 Men: 36.5% PLHIV 17%	Mean BCM in kg (SD) – HIV+ Men Mean BCM in kg (SD) – HIV- Men Mean BCM in kg (SD) – HIV+ Women Mean BCM in kg (SD) – HIV- Women	22.8 (4.6); N = 93 23.0 (4.1); N = 145 15.6 (2.4); N = 103 17.3 (2.5); N = 104	25.7 (3.1); N = 22 26.4 (3.9); N = 160 17.9 (2.2); N = 61 16.2 (2.3); N = 256	MWU P< 0.001 MWU P< 0.001 MWU P< 0.001 M–W U test P< 0.001	Unadjusted
Lean Mass Index (LMI) Kg/m ² (BIA)	Mupere (2012a)	Uganda, urban, outpatient TB clinics	2007-2008	Ambulatory smear/culture+ pTB Mean age: 27.9 Men 44% PLHIV: 49%	HIV- Neighbourhood random selection HIV+ clinic recruitment Mean age: 28.1 Men: 48.5% PLHIV: 56%	Mean LMI in kg/m ² (SD)– HIV+ Men Mean LMI in kg/m ² (SD)–HIV- Males Mean LMI in kg/m ² (SD)–HIV+ Women Mean LMI in kg/m ² (SD)–HIV+ Women	16.6(1.3) – N = 10 16.6(1.5) – N = 18 15.4(0.9) – N = 21 16.1(0.9) – N = 14	18.3(1.2) – N = 17 18.6(1.4) – N = 16 16.6(1.2) – N = 21 16.6(1.1)– N = 14	MWU P< 0.001 MWU P< 0.001 MWU P< 0.001 MWU P< 0.001	Unadjusted
	Mupere (2012b)	Uganda, urban. Clinical setting unknown	1999-2012	pTB, smear/culture+ (100%) Mean age not reported; 59% ≤30 years. Men: 41% PLHIV 52%	None	Proportion with low lean mass index (LMI), %, (n/N) – all with TB. Proportion with low lean mass index (LMI) %, (n/N) –Men Proportion with low lean mass index (LMI) %, (n/N) –Women Low LMI defined as <16.7 Kg/m ² for men, <14.6 Kg/m ² for women	33% (103/311) 50% (82/164) 14% (21/147)	No comparator group without TB	χ ² test, p<0.05 between sexes "Men had significantly greater proportion of individuals with reduced LMI compared to women"	Unadjusted
T12 skeletal muscle index (T12 SMI)	Huang (2025)[37]	China, urban, hospital inpatients	2020-2023	pTB, comorbidities excluded (HIV, COPD, Diabetes) Median age 43 Men: 70% PLHIV – exclusion, not known if testing done.	No comparator group	Low T12 SMI (<28.8cm ² /m ² for men and <20.8cm ² /m ² for women), % (n/N) – Overall Low T12 SMI, % (n/N) – Men Low T12 SMI, % (n/N) – Women	25.9% (80/309) 31.9% (69/216) 11.8% (11/93)	-	Low SMI group: higher age, lower % female, lower BMI, increased cavitation on CXR<0.05 (t or rank sum tests)	Unadjusted

									No diff smoking, alcohol, education	
After completion of treatment (not stated exact internal post treatment)										
Body cell mass (BCM), Kg (BIA)	Swaminathan (2008)[73]	India, urban outpatient clinics	2003-2000	PLHIV with culture/smear + pTB, completed treatment (in RCT setting) Mean age:31.5 across all participants (TB and comparator groups) Men: 76% PLHIV: 100%	PLHIV participants from RCT of LTBI treatment regimens, without evidence of TB No reported matching Men: 42% PLHIV 100%	Mean BCM in kg (SD), – Men Mean BCM in kg (SD), – Women	21.4 (3.3)– N = 124 15.2 (2.0)– N = 50	22.3 (3.4)– N = 161 15.3(2.2)– N = 327	No significant difference (Bonferroni test)	Unadjusted
Assessments of muscle function										
Before/at start of treatment										
Hand Grip Strength (HGS) (Kg)	Praygod (2011)[67]	Tanzania, urban; outpatient clinics	2006-2009	Smear+ pTB (100%) Mean age: 34.2 Men: 75.7% PLHIV% 47%	Age and sex matched, randomly selected, community controls. Mean age: 33.9 Men: 75.7% PLHIV% 10%	Mean HGS in kg (SD)– Men Mean HGS in kg (SD) – Women	29.0(NR) – N = 193 20.9(NR) – N = 162	36.0(NR) – N = 193 28.5(NR)– N = 162	Multivariable analyses, Mean difference. -6.8(-5.2, -8.3), P= 0.03 -6.8(5.2;8.4) P<0,001	Adjusted for age, HIV
Hand Grip Strength (HGS) (kg)	Paton (2006)[71]	Singapore, urban, outpatients	1999-2000	Men with culture confirmed pTB and wasting (BMI<20) Mean age 38.6 Men: 100% PLHIV: 56%	Hospital staff, blood donors Mean age 39.3 Men: 100% %PLHIV 50 Hep B carriers 15%	Mean HGS in kg (SD)	29.8(8.8)– N = 18	39.9(5.8)– N = 22	T test, p<0.001	Unadjusted
Hand Grip Strength (HGS) (kg)	Mishra (2023)[74]	India, urban, outpatient clinics (DOTS)	2019-2020	Smear+ pTB. HIV exclusion criteria Mean age 30.0 %male: 72 PLHIV: exclusion	Hospital/academic staff Mean age 32. %Male unknown %PLHIV unknown	Mean HGS in kg (SD)	27.1(9.1) – N = 101	34.4(6.5)	One way ANOVA P<0.01	Unadjusted
Hand Grip Strength (HGS) (kg)	Harries (1985)[68]	Nigeria, rural, inpatients	1984	Mainly smear+(73%) pTB Mean age 29 Men: 62% PLHIV: unknown %	Hospital staff Age, and sex matched. Mean Age: unknown Men: unknown% PLHIV: unknown %	Mean HGS in kg (SD) –Men) Mean HGS in kg (SD) – Women	24.0(9.1)– N = 54 17.0(7.9)– N = 32	42.0(5.8) – N = 54 26.0(5.8)– N = 32	T test, p<0.001 T test, p<0.001	Unadjusted
Hand Grip Strength (HGS)	Nkhoma (1987)[65]	Malawi, Nigeria, urban inpatients	Unknown	Smear+ pTB (87%) Mean age 35.0 Men: 100% PLHIV: exclusion	None	Malawi Mean HGS in Kg (SD) – Men Mean HGS in Kg (SD) –Women, Nigeria Mean HGS in Kg (SD) –Men, Mean HGS in Kg (SD) –Women,	29.9(9.9) 23(7.7) 24(9.1) 17(6.9)	No comparator group without TB	NA	NA
Assessments of physical performance										
Before/at start of treatment										
Chair stands in 10s (N)	Paton (2006)[71]	Singapore, urban, outpatients	1999-2000	Men with culture confirmed pTB and wasting (BMI<20)	Hospital staff, blood donors Mean age 39.3	Mean number of chair stands completed in 10 seconds (SD)	4.9(1.2)– N = 18	6.5(1.0)– N = 22	T test, p<0.001	Unadjusted

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				Mean age 38.6 Men: 100% PLHIV: 56%	Men: 100% PLHIV: 50% Hep B carriers 15%					
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Abbreviations and units: Adj., adjusted; AMA, arm muscle area (cm²); AMC, arm muscle circumference (cm); ANOVA, analysis of variance; BCM, body cell mass (kg); BIA, bioelectrical impedance analysis; BMI, body mass index (kg/m²); CD4, cluster of differentiation 4 (cells/μL); CI, confidence interval; COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease; CRP, C-reactive protein (mg/dL); CXR, chest X-ray; DM, diabetes mellitus; DOTS, directly observed therapy, short-course; DXA, dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry; FFM, fat-free mass (kg or % body weight); HGS, hand-grip strength (kg); HIV, human immunodeficiency virus; IQR, interquartile range; LBM, lean body mass (kg); LMI, lean mass index (kg/m²); MAMC, mid-arm muscle circumference (cm); MWU, Mann-Whitney U test; NA, not applicable; NR, not reported; PLHIV, people living with HIV; PLSD, protected least significant difference test; pTB, pulmonary tuberculosis; RCT, randomized controlled trial; SD, standard deviation; SEM, standard error of the mean; SES, socioeconomic status; SMI, skeletal muscle index (cm²/m²); TB, tuberculosis.

Table 3: Longitudinal studies reporting muscle deficits in pulmonary TB with and without comparator groups without TB.

Measurement / Timepoints	Author (period of recruitment) [Ref]	Country & setting	Period of recruitment	PWTB	Comparators	Measurement	Outcome: N		Statistical test	Adjustment
							PWTB	Control		
Assessments of muscle mass using anthropometric measures										
Arm Muscle Area (AMA) Baseline, 1 and 2 months	Harries (1986)[75]	Malawi, rural, inpatients	1986	Ambulant, smear+ pTB Mean age: 38 Men: 60% PLHIV: unknown%	Otherwise, healthy outpatients from same district and 'social stratum'. Age and sex matched Mean age: unknown Men 60% PLHIV unknown%	Mean AMA – Males Baseline 1 month 2 months Mean AMA – Females Baseline 4 weeks 8 weeks	32.5(6.9); N = 73 34.1 (NR); N = 73 34.9 (NR); N = 73 27.4 (6.5); N = 49 28.4 (NR); N = 49 29.6 (NR); N = 49	48.4(8.6) N = 73 37.4 N = 49	T-tests PWTB vs contr P<0.001 4w vs BL P<0.001 8w vs 4w P<0.001 PWTB vs contr P<0.001 4w vs BL P<0.05 8w vs 4wP<0.001	Unadjusted
Arm Muscle Area (AMA) Baseline, 8 weeks and 5 months	Praygod (2011)[76]	Tanzania, urban outpatient clinics	2006-2009	Adults with pTB Control arm of TB nutrition RCT Mean age: 37.3(14.0) Men: X% PLHIV: XX%	None	Mean AMA Baseline 2 months 5 months	35.3; N = 432 37.9; N = 391 41.6; N = 360		Difference in means (CI) 2m vs BL +2.50 (1.88,3.12) 5m vs baseline +5.89 (5.17,6.60); P value NR	Unadjusted
Arm Muscle Area (AMA) Baseline, 1 and 2 months	De Moraes (2014)[33]	Brazil, urban, hospital inpatient wards	2007-2008	Adults with pTB Mean age 38.4 Men%: X PLHIV: 0% (exclusion)	HIV-negative healthy people in the same city. No matching reported Characteristics unknown.	Mean AMA Baseline 1 month 2 months AMA defined muscle depletion (< 5th percentile reference[52])%(N) at baseline	26.1 (7.9); N = 35 28.7 (9.7); N = 35 31.8 (11.9); N = 35 91.4% (32/35)	55.2 (12.1); N = 35	T-tests BL vs cont P< 0.05 1m vs cont P< 0.05 2m vs cont P< 0.05	Unadjusted
Arm Muscle Circumference (AMC) Baseline 6 and 12 months (after admission)	Onwubalili et al (1988)[32]	United Kingdom, Urban hospital	2006-2009	Bacteriologically confirmed TB (73% pTB) Mean age 34.4 Male 67% PLHIV unknown%	Hospital staff. Matched in pairs by age, sex, ethnicity and diet. Characteristics unknown.	Mean AMC (SD) Baseline 6 months 12 months	21 (3); N = 30 22 (3); N = 21 22 (3); N = 15	24 (3); N = 30 24 (3); N = 21 24 (3); N = 15	T test vs controls P<0.001 vs controls P<0.05 vs controls P<0.001	Unadjusted pairwise comparisons
Arm Muscle Circumference	Faurholt-Jepsen (2012)[40]	Tanzania, urban, outpatient clinics	2006-2008	Smear +pTB, Mean age 36.3 Men 59.1% PLHIV: 48.9%	None	Mean AMC(CI) – nonDM Baseline 2 months 5 months	34.6 (34.0;35.1) N = 1008		Mean difference from multilevel mixed-effects linear regression (CI) 2m vs baseline: 2.7(2.2;3.1)	Adjusted for age, sex, HIV status, alpha-glycoprotein

Baseline, 2 and 5 months		(substudy of two RCTs)		Stratified by diabetes status		Mean AMC (CI) – DM Baseline 2 months 5 months	37.2(36.2;37.8); N = 1008 40.7(40.1;41.4); N = 1008 35.6(34.3;37.0)– N = 197 37.4(36.0;38.7)– N = 197 41.0(39.6;42.4)– N = 197		5m vs baseline: 6.2 (5.7;6.6)	smoking, alcohol, nutrition
Assessments of muscle mass using bioimpedance analysis (BIA)										
Lean mass (LM) from BIA Baseline, 3, 12 and 24 months	Mupere (2014)[43]	Uganda urban, outpatient clinics	2 studies pooled: 1)2002-2010 2)2003-2005	pTB (100% smear + culture+) with baseline wasting (men LMI<16.7kg/m2; women <14.6kg/m2) Mean age unknown; 63% ≤30 years. Male: 51.8% PLIHV: 43.2%	None	Mean LM(SD)–men Baseline 3 months 12 months 24months Mean LM (SD)–women Baseline 3 months 12 months 24months,	45.0(4.8) – N = 75 47.8(5.5) – N = NR 48.0(5.7) – N = NR 47.5(5.6) – N = NR 36.4(2.6) – N = 19 38.4(3.3) – N = NR 38.5(3.0) – N = NR 40.8(4.1) – N = NR	%change (vs prev visit): +6.6(6.3) -0.3(4.8) +0.4(4.1) - NA +6.3% (4.6) -1.5% (4.6) +1.2(4.3)	NR	NA
Fat-Free Mass (FFM), Kg (% body wt.) Baseline, 1 and 3 months	Frediani (2016)[42]	Georgia, urban, outpatients	2012-2024	pTB, smear and culture+ Cohort substudy of placebo arm of vitamin D trial Mean age 36 Male: 64%	Household contacts; patient attendees Mean age: 41 Male: 33% PLHIV% unknown	Mean FFM (SD) Baseline 2 months 4 months	48.3(11.0) – N = 94 49.1(12.5) – N = 83 51.5(10.7) – N = 83	49.5 (12.5)- N = 36	P<0.01 (T test and	Age sex, employment status and smoking
Lean mass from BIA (LM), kg Baseline, 1 and 2 months	Montalvo (2018)[77]	Peru, urban, hospital inpatients (at point of diagnosis)	2012-2024	Smear/culture + pTB Mean age 36.6 Men: 69% PLHIV: XX% Results stratified by outcome: "died" and "cured"	None	Mean FFM (SD)- died baseline 1month 2months Mean FFM (SD)- cured baseline 1months 2 months	46.1(9.3) – N = 17 47.7(9.9) – N = 12 46.5(9.8) – N = 8 45.6(9.9) –N = 108 45.7(9.9) – N = 108 45.9(9.8) – N = 108		Adjusted mixed linear models: Those who died lost 0.8kg of lean mass (p=0.008) by month 1 Survivors gained fat (1.2kg, p<0.001) and 1.3kg weight (p<0.001) but not lean mass (p=0.59)	Adjusted for age, sex, drug susceptibility and CD4 count.
Assessments of muscle mass using dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DXA)										
Fat-free mass from DXA, (FFM), kg Baseline, 1 and 6 months	Schwent (2004)[44]	United Kingdom, urban, hospital (invs outpatients unknown)	1999-2000	pTB, 77% smear or culture+ Mean age 42.3 Men: 70% PLHIV: 0% of known status (excluded)	None	Mean FFM (SD)- men Baseline 1month 6months Mean FFM (SD)- women Baseline 2 months 6 months	47.2(4.7) – N = 21 47.9(5.0) – N = 21 48.9(4.0) – N = 21 34.3(3.1) – N = 9 35.3(3.0) – N = 9 35.3(3.0) – N = 9		Results combined for males/females: 1 vs 0 month – no sig change 6 vs 1 month – no sig change 6 vs 1 month P<0.01	Repeated measures linear model, time and sex as ind variables after Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons

Assessments of muscle mass using Deuterium dilution											
Fat-free mass index (FFMI) using Deuterium dilution Baseline and 2 months	Praygod (2015)[45]	Tanzania, urban, outpatients	2007-2008	Smear + (69%) pTB Mean age 37.3 Men: 61.2% PLHIV: 45.7%	None	FFMI mean % gain vs baseline(95%CI) Men Women	 +0.9kg/m2(0.6;1.3) – N = 116 +0.2kg/m2(-0.2;0.6) – N = 116			P<0.001 (men) P=0.35: no change	Effects maintain after adjustment for age, sex, baseline FFMI, HIV/ART status, smoking, alcohol use, socioeconomic status, pulmonary status, trial arm, and CRP
Protein mass (% of body wt) (by Deuterium dilution) Baseline, 1 and 6 months	Schwent (2004)[19]	United Kingdom, urban, hospital (unclear if in- vs outpatients)	1999-2000	pTB, 77% smear or culture+ Mean age 42.3 Men: 70% PLHIV: 0% (excluded if status known)	None	Mean PM as %body weight (SD), men Baseline 1 month 6 months Mean PM as %body weight (SD), women Baseline 1 month 6 months	 19.8(4.3) – N = 21 18.9(4.2) – N = 21 19.6(4.0) – N = 21 13.6(5.9) – N = 9 12.8(5.7) – N = 9 12.8(4.5) – N = 9			Changes between time points (combined men and women): 1 vs 0 month – no sig change 6 vs 1 month – no sig change 6 vs 1 month – no sig change	Repeated measures linear model, time and sex as ind variables after Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons
Assessments of muscle function											
Handgrip Strength (HGS), Kg Baseline, 1 and 2 months	Harries (1988)[75]	Malawi, rural, inpatients	1986	Ambulant, smear+ pTB inpatients. Mean age: 38 Men: 60% PLHIV: unknown%	Outpatients from same district and 'social stratum'. Age and sex matched. Mean age unknown Men: 60% PLHIV: unknown%	Mean HGS (SD), men Baseline 1 month 2 months Mean HGS (SD), men Baseline 1 month 2 months	 29.9(9.7) N = 73 31.7 - N = 73 32.7 - N = 73 23.3(8.6) N = 49 24.5 - N = 49 26.0 - N = 49	36.5(9.9) N = 73 - - 32.1(7.9) -N = 49 - -		T test P<0.05 (vs cont) T test P<0.05 (vs bl) T test P<0.001 (vs wk4) T test P<0.001 (vs cont) No sig diff vs baseline T test P<0.05 (vs wk4)	Unadjusted
Handgrip Strength (HGS), Kg Baseline and 3 months	Jahnvi (2010)[46]	India, rural outpatient clinics	2005	Smear/culture+ pTB Mean age: 39.5 Men: 76% HIV exclusion	None	Mean HGS (SD), Baseline 3 months: change vs baseline (SD)	 20.0(1.5)–N = 50 +2.4(0.9)–N = unknown			No sig test reported/ difference not commented on	NA
Handgrip Strength (HGS), Kg Baseline, 2 and 5 months	Praygod (2011)[76]	Tanzania, urban outpatient clinics	2006-2009	Adults with pTB Control arm of TB nutrition RCT Mean age: 37.3(14.0) Men: X% %PLHIV: XX	None	Mean HGS (95% CI), Baseline 2 months 5 months	 26.2(25.4;26.9) N = 431 27.3(26.3;28.2) N = 392 30.4(29.5;31.3) N = 359			2mo: +1.00kg (0.48,1.54) vs baseline (mean increase) 5mo: +4.14kg (3.56,4.73) vs baseline	Unadjusted

Handgrip Strength (HGS), Kg Baseline, 2 and 5 months	Faurholt-Jepsen (2012)[40]	Tanzania, urban, outpatient clinics (substudy of two RCTs)	2006-2008	Smear +pTB, Mean age 36.3 %Men 59.1 PLHIV%: 48.9% Stratified by diabetes mellitus (DM) status	None	Mean HGS (CI) – NonDM Baseline 2 months 5 months Mean HGS (CI) – DM Baseline 2 months 5 months	25.8(25.3;26.3)– N = 1008 27.6(27.2;28.1)– N = 1008 30.5(30.0;30.9)– N = 1008 25.2(24.2;26.2)– N = 197 26.8(25.7;27.9)– N = 197 29.6(28.5;30.7)– N = 197		2mo: Mean diff (95%CI) vs baseline: +1.8 (1.5;2.2) 5mo: Mean diff (95%CI) vs baseline +4.7 (4.3;5.0)	Multilevel mixed-effects linear regression; adjusted for age, sex, HIV status, alpha-glycoprotein smoking, alcohol, nutrition
Handgrip Strength (HGS), Kg Baseline, 2 and 5 months	Mishra (2021)[34]	India, urban, outpatients	2019-2020	pTB, 70% micro confirmed Mean age 32.2 Men 74% PLHIV: 0% (exclusion)	Hospital staff; patient attendants. Mean age: 30 Men 56% PLHIV unknown%	Mean HGS (SEM) Baseline 2 months 5 months	28.1(1.9); N = 23 28.5(1.9); N = 23 30.9(2.0); N = 23	36.5(7.5)–N = 25	-8.32kg PTB vs control No sig changes vs baseline (P=1.00) Increase vs baseline P<0.001 Increase vs 2-month P<0.001	Repeated Measures ANOVA, Bonferroni correction. Unadjusted
Assessments of physical performance										
Chair stands completed in 10s (N) Baseline and 3 months	Jahnavi (2010)[46]	India, rural outpatient clinics	2005	Smear/culture+ pTB Mean age 39.5 Men 76% HIV exclusion	None	Mean chair stands in 10s (SD) Baseline 3 months	5.7(1.3)–N = 50 +1.9(0.4)–N = not stated		"Timed-stands test improved" Significance test NR	Unknown

Abbreviations and units: Adj., adjusted; AMA, arm muscle area (cm²); AMC, arm muscle circumference (cm); ANOVA, analysis of variance; AAG, α-1-acid glycoprotein; ART, antiretroviral therapy; BIA, bioelectrical impedance analysis; BMI, body mass index (kg/m²); BL, baseline; CD4, cluster of differentiation 4 (cells/μL); CI, confidence interval; CRP, C-reactive protein (mg/dL); DM, diabetes mellitus; DXA, dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry; FFM, fat-free mass (kg or % body weight); FFMI, fat-free mass index (kg/m²); HGS, hand-grip strength (kg); HIV, human immunodeficiency virus; LM, lean mass (kg); LMI, lean mass index (kg/m²); NA, not applicable; NonDM, non-diabetic; NR, not reported; pTB, pulmonary tuberculosis; PLHIV, people living with HIV; PM, protein mass (% body weight); RCT, randomized controlled trial; SD, standard deviation; SEM, standard error of the mean; SES, socioeconomic status; wk, week; mo, month.

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Table 4: Studies reporting on the impact of muscle deficits on TB treatment outcomes (n = 6 studies)

Study (Year)	Country & Setting	Study period	N	Population	Outcome (n with outcome)	Muscle measurements	Key Findings	Adjustment
Prospective cohort								
Montalvo (2018)[77]	Peru, urban, hospital outpatients under DOTS	2012-2014	125	PLHIV, ≥15, newly diagnosed pulmonary TB (smear/culture+) Mean age: 36.9 (SD13.5) Men: 69% PLHIV: 100% (inclusion) CD4 <200: 70% DM: not reported Mean BMI: Survivors: 20.9 Died: 22.1 Mean BMI 20.9 (in those who died)	Death (n = 17)	Lean muscle mass in kg using bioelectrical impedance analysis	Adjusted decrease in lean muscle mass was -1.59 (-2.98—0.19) kg at 2-month in people who died compared to those who survived	Adjusted for age, sex, drug susceptibility, and CD4 count.
Lee (2019)[78]	Philippines, urban, hospital inpatients	2016-2017	348	Adults with TB Men: 70% Mean age: 45 PLHIV: 6.3% (60% unknown) DM:17.7% Mean BMI:17.9	Death between 3-30 days of admission (n = 12)	Handgrip Strength (HGS) in kg	Univariable OR of death was 0.91 (95%CI 0.88-0.94) for each kg increase in HGS Increased HGS associated with decreased odds of mortality after adjustment(P<0.001)	Age, MUAC, immobility
Retrospective cohort								
Mupere (2012)[79]	Uganda, urban, outpatient/household	1995-2002	311	Adults with pulmonary TB Age >30 years: 38% Men: 52% PLHIV: 44% DM: NR Mean BMI: men = 18.6; women = 20.0 BMI<18.5: 40%	Death (n = 23)	Lean tissue mass index (kg/m ²) using bioelectrical impedance analysis	Adjusted HR of death comparing normal to low lean tissue mass index was 2.36 (95%CI 1.11-5.01) with evidence of effect modification by sex: women -HR 5.14 (95%CI 1.55-16.93) men – HR 1.05 (95%CI 0.040-2.77)	Adjusted for age, HIV status, weight loss history, smoking and chest x-ray severity
Tanaka (2021)[47]	Japan, hospital inpatients	2013-2016	258	Adults >65 with bacteriologically confirmed TB Median age: 84 Men: 50% PLHIV: unknown DM: Survivors:24% Died: 27%	Death (n = 71)	Erector spinae muscle area in mm ² using CT scan (ESMcsa)	Median ESMcsa in non-survivors 1306 (IQR 1042–1624) vs 1716 (IQR 1296–2328) in survivors Adjusted OR of death 0.0999(95%CI 0.999-1.000, P=0.127) did not show an	Adjusted for age, CRP, respiratory failure, and comorbidities

Study (Year)	Country & Setting	Study period	N	Population	Outcome (n with outcome)	Muscle measurements	Key Findings	Adjustment
Prospective cohort								
				Median BMI: Survivors: 19.1 Non survivors: 17.8			association between ESM and mortality.	
Huang (2025)[37]	China, urban, hospital inpatients	2020-2023	309	Adults with microbiologically confirmed TB Exclusion of people with comorbidities (HIV, COPD, diabetes) Median age: 43 (range: 18-93) Men: 70% DM: exclusion criteria Median BMI: Low muscle group: 17.9 Normal muscle group: 21.4	Death or failure (N = 47)	T12 skeletal muscle index (T12 SMI) using CT scan	Adjusted OR of death comparing normal with low muscle mass was 20.10 (95%CI 8.81-51.55)	Adjusted for age, gender and T12 skeletal muscle radiation attenuation (T12 SMRA)
Shimoda (2023)[48]	Japan, urban, hospital inpatients	2019-2021	267	Adults >65 with pulmonary TB Median age: Survivors:80 Died 86.0 Men: 60% PLHIV: NR DM: NR Median BMI: Survivors: 18.1 Died: 16.5	Death (n = 40)	Erector spinae muscle area in mm ² using CT scan (ESMcsa)	Median ESMcsa in non-survivors 670 (IQR 585-761) vs 914 (IQR 718-1142) in survivors Adjusted HR of death 0.998 (95%CI 0.996-0.999) for every mm ² increase in ESMcsa	Adjusted for BMI, CRP, albumin, ALT, miliary pattern of TB on CT, treatment regimen and comorbidities

Abbreviations: ALT, alanine aminotransferase (IU/L); AOR, adjusted odds ratio (unitless); BIA, bioelectrical impedance analysis; BMI, body mass index (kg/m²); BSA, body surface area (m²); CD4, cluster of differentiation 4 (cells/μL); CI, confidence interval; CKD, chronic kidney disease; CRP, C-reactive protein (mg/dL); CT, computed tomography; DM, diabetes mellitus; DOTS, directly observed therapy, short course; ESMcsa, erector spinae muscle cross-sectional area (mm²); ESM, erector spinae muscle; HGS, hand-grip strength (kg); HR, hazard ratio (unitless); HIV, human immunodeficiency virus; IQR, interquartile range; MAC, *Mycobacterium avium* complex; MUAC, mid-upper arm circumference (cm); NR, not reported; OR, odds ratio (unitless); PLHIV, people living with HIV; SD, standard deviation; SMI, skeletal muscle index (cm²/m² or mm²/m², as reported); SMRA, skeletal muscle radiation attenuation (Hounsfield units, HU); TB, tuberculosis.

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Table 5: Studies reporting on the impact of interventions on muscle deficits in pulmonary TB.

Study (Year)	Country & Setting	Study period	Population	Intervention	Control	Outcomes:	Key Findings
Randomised controlled trials							
Praygod (2012)[80]	Tanzania, outpatient TB clinics	2006-2009	100% Smear + pTB Mean age: 35.4 Male: 50% PLHIV: 100% (inclusion) CD<350: 69% Mean BMI 18.6	N = 189 6 biscuits/day (880 kcal; 27 g protein) + micronutrient supplementation for 2mo from start of treatment	N = 188 1 biscuit/day (150 kcal; 4.5 g protein) + micronutrient supplementation for 2mo	Primary: Weight gain at 2 and 5 months Muscle: Arm fat area, arm muscle area, handgrip strength at 2 and 5mo	Intervention had no significant effect on weight, arm muscle or fat area; marginal, non-significant increase in handgrip strength at 5 months (+1.3kg, P+0.07)
PrayGod (2011)[76]	Tanzania; urban outpatient TB clinics	2006-2009	56% smear+ pTB Mean age: 37 (range 15-89) Men: 63% PLHIV: 28% Mean (SD) BMI 18.9 (3.0)	N = 433 Energy protein biscuit (4.5g protein, 615kJ) + multiple micronutrients for 60d.	N = 432 Energy protein biscuit without micronutrients	Primary: weight gain at 2 and 5mo Muscle: arm muscle area and handgrip strength (HGS) at 2 and 5 mo	No effect on primary outcome (weight gain) or arm muscle area at 2/5months At 2mo, HGS higher increase in micronutrient group vs controls (+1.2kg (95%CI 0.50, 1.94, P.001) but no difference at 5mo.
Jahnavi (2010)[46]	India, rural, outpatient TB clinics (DOTS)	2005	Smear/culture+ pTB Mean age 40 Men: 74% PLHIV: 0% (exclusion)	N = 50 Counselling + 600 kcal/6g protein daily & micronutrient rich foods for 3mo	N = 50 General advice only	Primary: not stated Muscle: Change in HGS 0–3mo	Weight gain higher in food supplement group (8.6%) vs controls (2.8%) (t=5.9, P<0.001) Increase in HGS higher in supplement group (t=6.13, p<0.001)
Paton (2004)[81]	Singapore; urban outpatient TB unit	2002-2004	61% culture+ pTB PLHIV: 0% (exclusion) Diabetes: 0% (exclusion) BMI<20 as inclusion criteria	N = 19 Counselling + 600 kcal/6g protein daily & micronutrient rich foods for 3mo	N = 17 General advice only	Primary: Lean mass measured by DXA scan 0-6wks Muscle: HGS and lean mass at 0,6,12,24wks	Significant increase in lean mass and HGS 6 weeks vs control (ANCOVA; ITT) No difference in lean mass/HGS at 12 or 24 weeks

Abbreviations and units: Adj., adjusted; ANCOVA, analysis of covariance; BMI, body mass index (kg/m²); CD4, cluster of differentiation 4 (cells/μL); CI, confidence interval; DOTS, directly observed therapy, short-course; DXA, dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry; HGS, hand-grip strength (kg); HIV, human immunodeficiency virus; ITT, intention-to-treat; kcal, kilocalorie; kJ, kilojoule; mo, month; NR, not reported; PWTB, people with tuberculosis; PLHIV, people living with HIV; SD, standard deviation; TB, tuberculosis; wk, week.

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935 **Supplementary File 1: Search strategies (Skeletal Muscle, Cachexia and Pulmonary Tuberculosis: a**
 936 **scoping review)**

937 **Searches and timing:**
 938

Information Source	Platform/Database	Search Coverage	Final Search Date
MEDLINE	Ovid	Inception–2025	03 September 2025
Embase	Embase.com	Inception–2025	03 September 2025
Web of Science Core Collection	Web of Science	Inception–2025	03 September 2025
Africa Journals Online	AJOL	Inception–2025	03 September 2025
Google Search	Google (Web)	No limits	03 September 2025
World Health Organization Website	WHO.int	Inception–2025	03 September 2025
Initial Scoping Search	All sources above	Inception–Dec 2024	Dec 2024

939

940 **Strategies:**

941 **Database: MEDLINE (Ovid)**

942 **Date of search:** 03 September 2025

943 **Coverage: Inception to** 03 September 2025

944 **Search strategy:**

- 945 1. exp Tuberculosis/ OR exp Tuberculosis, Pleural/ OR exp Mycobacterium tuberculosis/
 946 OR exp Tuberculosis, Multidrug-Resistant/ OR exp Latent Tuberculosis/
 947 OR exp Tuberculosis, Extrapulmonary/ OR exp Tuberculosis, Pulmonary/
 948 2. Tuberculosis.ti,ab,kw.
- 949 3. exp Antitubercular Agents/
 950 4. (antitubercular agent*).ti,ab,kw.
- 951 5. exp Tuberculosis, Multidrug-Resistant/
 952 6. (multidrug-resistant).ti,ab,kw.
- 953 7. exp Cachexia/
 954 8. cachexia.ti,ab,kw.
- 955 9. exp Body Composition/ OR exp Muscle, Skeletal/ OR exp Sarcopenia/
 956 OR exp Muscular Atrophy/
 957 10. (sarcopenia OR muscular OR muscle).ti,ab,kw.
- 958 11. ("body composition" OR "lean mass" OR wasting OR atrophy).ti,ab,kw.
- 959 12. exp Malnutrition/
 960 13. (malnutrition OR undernutrition OR malnourished).ti,ab,kw.
- 961 14. exp Muscle Strength/
 962 15. exp Hand Strength/ OR "grip strength".ti,ab,kw.
- 963 16. exp Muscle Power/ OR "muscle power".ti,ab,kw.
- 964 17. 2 AND 6
- 965 18. 1 OR 2 OR 3 OR 4 OR 5 OR 17
- 966 19. 7 OR 8 OR 9 OR 10 OR 11 OR 12 OR 13 OR 14 OR 15 OR 16
- 967 20. 18 AND 19
- 968 21. limit 20 to (humans AND "all adults")

969 **Database:** Embase (Embase.com)

970 **Date of search:** 03 September 2025

971 **Coverage:** Inception to 03 September 2025

972 **Search strategy:**

- 973 1. exp Tuberculosis/ OR exp Tuberculosis, Pleural/ OR exp Mycobacterium tuberculosis/
 974 OR exp Tuberculosis, Multidrug-Resistant/ OR exp Latent Tuberculosis/
 975 OR exp Extensively Drug-Resistant Tuberculosis/ OR exp Tuberculosis, Extrapulmonary/
 976 OR exp Tuberculosis, Pulmonary/
 977 2. Tuberculosis.ti,ab,kw.
- 978 3. exp Antitubercular Agents/
 979 4. (antitubercular agent*).ti,ab,kw.
- 980 5. exp Cachexia/
 981 6. cachexia.ti,ab,kw.
- 982 7. exp Body Composition/ OR exp Muscle, Skeletal/ OR exp Sarcopenia/ OR exp Muscular Atrophy/
 983 8. Sarcopenia.ti,ab,kw.
- 984 9. ("body composition" OR "lean mass" OR wasting OR atrophy).ti,ab,kw.
- 985 10. exp Muscle Strength/ OR exp Hand Strength/ OR "grip strength".ti,ab,kw.
 986 OR "muscle power".ti,ab,kw.

988 11. 1 OR 2 OR 3 OR 4
989 12. 5 OR 6 OR 7 OR 8 OR 9 OR 10
990 13. 11 AND 12
991 14. limit 13 to humans
992 15. limit 14 to adult (18 to 64 years)
993
994 **Database:** Web of Science Core Collection
995 **Date of search:** 03 September 2025
996 **Coverage:** Inception to 03 September 2025
997 **Search strategy:**
998 TS=(
999 Tuberculosis OR
1000 "Pulmonary Tuberculosis" OR
1001 "Pleural Tuberculosis" OR
1002 "Multidrug-Resistant Tuberculosis" OR
1003 "Latent Tuberculosis" OR
1004 "Extensively Drug-Resistant Tuberculosis" OR
1005 "Extrapulmonary Tuberculosis" OR
1006 "Mycobacterium tuberculosis" OR
1007 "antitubercular agent"
1008)
1009 AND
1010 TS=(
1011 Cachexia OR
1012 Sarcopenia OR
1013 "Body Composition" OR
1014 "Lean Mass" OR
1015 "Wasting" OR
1016 Atrophy OR
1017 "Muscular Atrophy" OR
1018 "Muscle Strength"
1019)
1020 **Database:** African Journals Online (AJOL)
1021 **Date of search:** 03 September 2025
1022 **Coverage:** Inception to 03 September 2025
1023 **Search strategy:**
1024 Search 1 – Cachexia + tuberculosis
1025 Search 2 – Muscle + tuberculosis
1026 Search 3 – Sarcopenia + tuberculosis
1027
1028 **Source:** Google Search (Web)
1029 **Date of search:** 03 September 2025
1030 **Coverage:** Not limited by date
1031 **Search strategy (first 100 hits screened for each query):**
1032 Cachexia and Tuberculosis
1033 Sarcopenia and Tuberculosis
1034 Muscle and Tuberculosis
1035 Grip Strength and Tuberculosis
1036
1037 **Supplementary Table 1: Summary of risk factors and associations with skeletal muscle deficits**
1038 **in pulmonary TB (at TB diagnosis)**

Factor	Association with muscle mass		Association with muscle function	
	N	Summary of findings	N	Summary of findings
Demographics, co-morbidities, and nutritional factors				
Sex (male)	3	Two studies reported that more men with TB had low muscle mass vs women at TB diagnosis ([61, 82]); one reported higher	0	

		muscle mass indices among men compared to women at baseline (not accounting for sex-specific norms); and greater increase from TB diagnosis to 2 months [45, 83].		
Smoking	3	One study identified an association between smoking and low LMI at baseline; but this was not adjusted for confounding. Two further studies found no association. One study identified a trend toward less gain in FFMI (baseline to 2 months) in current smokers vs never smokers (adjusted for HIV, smear grade and other confounders; p=0.08; [45].		
Alcohol use	1	No association with low T12 SMI[37]		
Diabetes	1	No association with AMA at baseline or follow up; nor with recovery trajectory in adjusted analyses[40]	1	No association with grip strength at baseline or follow up; nor with recovery in adjusted analyses[84].
SEP (Low)	2	Some evidence for an association between fewer assets and lower AMC[85] and FFMI[45]; but not with change in FFMI over time[45]	0	
Vegetarian diet	1	No difference in AMC by diet at baseline, or trajectory of AMC[32]		
HIV associated factors				
HIV status (positive)	11	3 studies identified a statistically significant association between positive HIV status and lower muscle mass (2/3 adjusted for confounding) (BCM[70, 85]MAMC: [63]but 6 did not find evidence of an association (1/6 adjusted for confounding (BCM: Shah (2001 [86]),[72], [82]), Paton (2006) [71]; LMI: Mupere (2012a [79])/Mupere (2014 [43])*; FFMI: PrayGod (2013 [83])) Two studies suggested effect modification by sex, with lower muscle mass among men living with HIV vs HIV- men; but no association in women (AMA: [66] (2010);	1	No association with grip strength or timed stands (Paton 2006)

		BCM Van Lettow (2005)/Van Lettow (2004 [87, 88])*. In the one study reporting change in FFMI over time, no association with HIV status was identified (Praygod [89] (2015)*).		
CD4 count (low)	4	1 study reported an association between low CD4 count (≤ 200) and lower BCM at TB diagnosis[86] but 3 found no association (PrayGod (2013); [83]Mupere (2010) [72]; Praygod (2012)[80] - none were adjusted for confounding. No difference in recovery of muscle mass during treatment by CD4 count (BCM Praygod (2012 [80]) and FFMI Praygod (2015 [45])*)	1	No clear differences in grip strength at baseline, or recovery during treatment among people with CD4 ≤ 350 vs higher (Praygod (2012 [80]))
HIV viral load (high)	0	-		-
Markers of inflammation and TB severity				
Radiographic severity	6	Lower muscle mass among people with extensive (3+lobes/cavities affected) vs more limited disease in 2 unadjusted analyses (AMA/AMC: Harries (1985 [68]); AMA: Harries (1988) [75] - not adjusted); in 1 study which adjusted for age, sex and HIV no association was seen (BCM: Van Lettow (2005)/Van Lettow (2004 [87, 88])* , but in another the association was seen in univariable and adjusted analyses (Huang (2025 [37])). One study suggested the opposite association (lower LMI in less advanced disease; Mupere (2012a [79])/Mupere (2014 [43])* Disease severity not correlated with muscle mass changes (p-ratio) during treatment (Schwenk (2004 [44]))	2	Lower grip strength among people with extensive vs more limited disease Harries (1985) Harries (1988) [68, 75]- not adjusted
Bacillary burden	2	No association with baseline muscle mass in 2 studies (adjusted for sex, age, HIV and markers of SEP; Villamor (2006 [85]) PrayGod (2013 [83])); no association with change in FFMI over time (Praygod (2015 [45])*)	0	

TB Symptom duration (long)	0	NA	-	-
Drug resistant TB	1	Higher odds of low PMI among people with MDR-TB vs DS-TB (OR 2.78; 1.45–5.31; p=0.002) in adjusted analyses (adjustment set not stated; Shin (2020) [90])	0	
TB culture conversion	1	No association between remaining culture positive at 30 or 60 days and AMA (Morales (2014 [33]))	0	
Inflammation/acute phase response	1	No statistically significant association was observed between the soluble receptor for advanced glycation end products (sRAGE) or Nε-(carboxymethyl)lysine (CML) and MAMC[36]; higher serum α1-antichymotrypsin associated with lower AMA [66]	0	

1039 **Footnotes:** * Mupere (2012a)/Mupere (2014) and Van Lettow (2005)/Van Lettow (2004) considered
1040 as one study as the underlying population was the same; Praygod(2015) reports follow up of the
1041 population reported in Praygod(2013) and these are considered one study. **Abbreviations:** AMA =
1042 arm muscle area; AMC = arm muscle circumference; BCM = body cell mass (measured with biometric
1043 impedance analysis); CML, Nε-(carboxymethyl)lysine (a predominant AGE biomarker); DS-TB = drug
1044 sensitive TB; FFMI = fat free mass index; LMI = lean mass index; MAMC = mid arm muscle
1045 circumference; MDR-TB = multi-drug resistant TB; N = number of studies; PMI = pectoralis muscle
1046 index (measured from computed tomography parameters); SEP = socio-economic position; sRAGE:
1047 soluble receptor for advanced glycation end products (circulating “decoy” receptor); SMI = skeletal
1048 muscle index

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Supplementary table 2: Risk factors for muscle impairment among people with pulmonary TB (n = 26 studies)

Study (Year)	Study Design / Timepoint(s)	Country & Setting	Period of data collection	Number of people with TB included	Population characteristics	Exposures of interest	Outcomes	Key Findings	Adjustment
Measures of mass and function									
<i>Demographics, comorbidities and nutritional factors</i>									
Faurholt-Jepsen (2012)[40]	RCT 0/2/5 months	Tanzania, urban outpatient TB clinics	2006–2008	1205	All pTB Mean age 37 Men: 59% PLHIV: 49% Diabetes: 16%	Diabetes	AMA Grip strength	Diabetes not associated with AMA or grip strength recovery at baseline or follow up; nor with recovery in AMA or grip strength in adjusted analyses.	Age, sex, HIV status, alpha-1 glycoprotein, smoking, alcohol intake, and trial arm.
Nkhoma (1987)[65]	Cross sectional	Malawi, Nigeria, urban inpatients	Unknown	168	Smear+ pTB (87%) Mean age 35.0 Men: 100% PLHIV exclusion	Country (Malawi vs Nigeria)	Arm muscle circumference and handgrip strength testing	Handgrip strength, but not arm muscle circumference, were higher in participants from Malawi. Unadjusted analyses (t-test; χ^2)	None
<i>HIV status</i>									
Paton (2006)[71]	Case-control (TB diagnosis)	Singapore, urban inpatient/outpatient	1999–2000	18	Adult men BMI <20 and/or >10% weight loss	HIV status	Lean mass (DEXA) Body cell mass (BIA) Grip strength	HIV status not associated with muscle mass measures (BCM in PLHIV 21.4±4.6 vs 20.4±2.3 in HIV-; Grip 28.1±8.2 vs 31.9±9.6; timed stands 4.6±1.2 vs 5.4±1.1; no formal statistical testing)	None
Praygod (2012)[80]	RCT (Baseline, 2 & 5 months)	Tanzania; urban outpatients	2006–2009	377 (116 with BIA)	All PTB, PLHIV Mean age: 35 Men 50% CD4≤350 69%	CD4 count	Arm muscle area Grip strength	No clear differences in AMA and grip strength at baseline, or recovery during treatment among people with CD4≤350 vs higher, with overlapping confidence intervals (no formal statistical testing).	None
<i>Markers of inflammation and TB severity</i>									
Harries (1985)[68]	Cross-sectional (TB diagnosis)	Nigeria, inpatients	2013-2016	84	pTB, 73% smear + Mean age 29–30 Men: 62% PLHIV unknown %extensive disease: 60%	Radiographic severity	Arm muscle area Arm muscle circumference Grip strength	Lower muscle mass and function among people with extensive (3+lobes/cavities affected) vs more limited disease: AMA 28.0±7.2 vs 37.8±7.5 in men and 24.4±7.4 vs 32.0±6.5 in women; AMC 74±9 vs 86±9 in men and 75±11 vs 86±9 in women; Grip strength 20±8.2 vs 29±7.8 in men and 15±6.4 vs 21±6.5 in women. 'All measurements significantly reduced in extensive disease (p<0.05, Student t-test).'	None
Harries (1988)[75]	Cross-sectional (TB diagnosis)	Malawi, inpatients	1986	122	Adults smear+ PTB Mean age: 29 Men: 62%	Radiographic severity	Arm muscle area Grip strength	Lower AMA and grip strength in extensive disease among women (5-6 zone; 25.7±5.4 and 19.9±8.3 respectively) vs limited (1-2 zones; 31.9±7.0 and 28.5±8.1; both P<0.05); among men trends were the same (5-6 zone; 31.1±6.3 and 29.8±8.7 respectively) vs limited (1-2 zones; 37.6±9.6 and 34.5±10.9) but not significant for grip strength (p<0.05 and p>0.05).	None No adjustment for multiple comparisons

								No consistent association across sputum grade or presence of cavitation.	
Measures of mass only									
<i>Demographics, comorbidities and nutritional factors</i>									
Metcalfe (2005)[61]	Case-control TB diagnosis	Sri Lanka, urban inpatients and outpatients (% inpatients unknown)	2002	50	All smear+ pTB Mean age: 50 Men: 60%	Sex	Clinical muscle wasting (temporalis & deltoid)	Men appeared to have higher prevalence of muscle wasting (temp 63 vs 40% & delt 57 vs 30%), but not statistically significant.	None
Onwubalili (1988)[32]	Prospective cohort (Baseline and 6m)	UK; inpatients	1984–1985 (approx.)	30	pTB; smear+ Mean age 34	Vegetarian diet	Arm muscle circumference (AMC) at baseline and 6 months	No difference in AMC by diet at baseline, or trajectory of AMC ('not significant')	None
<i>HIV status</i>									
Niyongabo (1994)[70]	Cross-sectional (TB diagnosis)	Burundi; urban inpatients	1993	67	All adults; smear+ PTB Mean age 33 Men 54% PLHIV: 84%	HIV status	Body cell mass (anthropometric formulas)	PLHIV had significantly lower BCM vs HIV-Unadjusted: 36.3 vs 40.4kg; p=0.01 (MWU) 'Significant' after adjustment	Sex
Shah (2001)[86]	Cross-sectional (TB diagnosis)	Uganda, urban outpatients	1999–2000	539	All adults; smear+ PTB Mean age ~29–32y; smear-positive PTB PLHIV 48%	HIV status CD4 count ≤200 vs >200 cells/μL (PLHIV only)	Body cell mass (BIA)	No BCM differences by HIV status (mean 21.9kg PLHIV vs 21.5 HIV-, p=0.25 in men; 16.2 vs 16.5, p=0.56 in women) Among PLHIV, CD4≤200 associated with lower BCM (mean 20.8kg CD4≤200 vs 22.2 higher, p=0.009 among men; 16.9 vs 15.4, p=0.009 among women).	None
Mupere (2010)[72]	Cross-sectional (TB diagnosis)	Uganda, urban outpatients	2002–2008	430	Adults; smear+ PTB PLHIV 44% Mean age ~30	HIV status CD4 count	Body cell mass (BIA)	HIV status not associated with BCM (no formal statistical testing) No difference by CD4 count (≤200cells/uL vs higher): p=0.9	None
Mupere (2012b)[82]	Cross-sectional (TB diagnosis)	Uganda; urban outpatients	2007–2008	63	All adults; smear/culture+ PTB Mean age 29 PLHIV 49%	HIV status	Lean tissue mass index (BIA)	No significant differences in LMI by HIV status among TB patients at baseline (p>0.05) Unadjusted Wilcoxon–Mann–Whitney group comparisons	None
Lazzari (2018)[63]	Cross-sectional (TB diagnosis)	Brazil, inpatients	Not reported	108	Adult with pTB Mean age: 45 Men: 71% PLHIV: 41%	HIV status	MAMC BIA	PLHIV had higher prevalence of low MAMC (75% vs 48%; p=0.010)	None
<i>Markers of inflammation and TB severity</i>									
Schwenk (2004)[44]	Prospective cohort	UK; urban, not stated if inpatient/outpatients	1999–2000	30	Adults; pTB Mean age 43 Men 70% Cavitation 37%	Radiographic severity	Protein mass (PM) and p-ratio (proportion of energy stored as protein) via 4-component model	Disease severity not correlated with muscle mass changes (p-ratio) during treatment	None

Moraes (2014)[33]	Prospective cohort (Baseline, 1 month 2 months)	Brazil; inpatient referral TB hospitals	2007-2008	35	Men; smear/culture+ pTB Mean age 38.4; PLHIV excluded	Response to treatment (TB culture conversion)	Arm Muscle Area (AMA)	No association between remaining culture positive at 30 or 60 days and AMA (p>0.05)	None
Shin (2020)[91]	Case-control	South Korea; Gyeongsang National University Hospital	2010-2016	180	Adults; pTB MDR-TB: 50% HIV excluded	Drug resistance status	Pectoralis muscle index (PMI) via chest CT	Lower PMI in MDR-TB vs DS-TB (mean 61.7mm ² /kg/m ² ±16.7 vs 79.0±19.2; p<0.001) Higher odds of low PMI (<68.2) among people with MDR-TB vs DS-TB (OR 2.78; 1.45-5.31; p=0.002) in adjusted analyses	Adjustment set not stated
Da Silva (2019)[36]	Case-control	Brazil, urban, inpatients	2017-2018	35	pTB; 80% smear + Mean age: 38 Men: 69% PLHIV 40%	Serum sRAGE and AGE-CML	MAMC	No association between sRAGE/CML and MAMC	None
Multiple									
Range (2010)[66]	Cross-sectional (TB diagnosis)	Tanzania, rural outpatients	2001-2002	532	Adults; smear+ PTB Mean age 35 Men 59% PLHIV 44%	HIV status Serum α1-antichymotrypsin (ACT)	Arm muscle area (AMA)	HIV associated with lower AMA in men (36.5cm ² vs 34.6; adj p=0.02) but not women (31.7 vs 31.8; adj p=0.96); higher ACT associated with lower AMA in both sexes (adj p<0.01 for linear trend) Adjusted linear regression (age, height)	Age and height; AMA additionally for TB status, HIV
Mupere (2012a) and Mupere (2014) [43, 79]	Retrospective cohort (TB diagnosis)	Uganda; urban outpatients	2002-?	311	Adults; smear/culture+ PTB Mean age: NR (62% ≤30) Men: 53% PLHIV: 44%	Sex HIV status Anaemia Radiographic extent Smoking	Lean tissue mass index (BIA) Low LMI defined as <16.7 kg/m ² for men and <14.6 kg/m ² for women	52% men (n = 164) vs 14% women (n = 147) low LMI (p<0.001) No difference in low LMI by HIV status (34% PLHIV (n = 138) vs 33% HIV- (n = 172); p>0.05) No difference in low LMI by anaemia (35% Hb≤10g/dL (n = 74) vs 33% higher (n = 224); p>0.05) Radiographic extent associated with lower prevalence of low LMI (36% moderate/far advanced (n = 257) vs 100% mild (n = 10); p<0.05) Smoking associated with higher prevalence of low LMI (57% smokers (n = 72) vs 26% non-smokers (n = 238); p<0.001) Alcohol associated with higher prevalence of low LMI (41% drinkers (n = 95) vs 30% non-drinkers (n = 215); p<0.05) Men with wasting regained LMI at a greater rate (4.55kg/m ² /month (95%CI 1.26-7.83) vs women (2.07 (95%CI -0.74-4.88) during the first 3 months of treatment. No difference in LMI trajectory by HIV status (2.93 (2.23-3.63) vs 1.75 (0.94-2.55).	None No adjustment for multiple comparisons HIV, anaemia, smoking, history of weight loss, radiographic extent.
PrayGod (2013)/Praygod (2015) *[45, 83]	Cross-sectional (TB diagnosis)/Cohort (+2m)	Tanzania, urban outpatients	2007-2008	201	Adults; pTB (65% sputum+). Mean age: 36.8 Men: 62% PLHIV: 52% (13% ART) Smokers: 24%	Sputum bacillary burden Sex Smoking SES HIV status CD4 ART	Fat-free mass index (FFM-I) via D2O dilution	Men had 1.5-kg/m ² (95%CI 0.9, 2.0; p<0.0001) higher FFMI vs women. Alcohol (-0.01; -0.6, 0.5; p=0.98), current smoking (-0.3; 95%CI -0.7, 0.6; p=0.93) not associated with lower FFMI.	Sex, age, alcohol, smoking, assets, smear+/-, HIV (sex/age only adjusted)

					Alcohol 54%	pulmonary TB status		Greater household asset ownership may be protective (0.7; -0.1, 1.6; p=0.07 5-6 vs 0-2 assets). No association with smear positivity (-0.3; -0.8, 0.3; p=0.35) or HIV status (0.1; -0.4, 0.7; p=0.64). CD4 count 'not associated; with FFMI Men gained more FFM to 2 months of treatment compared to women (coeff of change in FFMI 0.7; 0.2, 1.3; p=0.01). Trend towards less change among current smoker's vs non (-0.5; -1.2, 0.07; p=0.08) No difference in change by SEP (p>0.6), smear status (p=0.25), HIV status (p=0.85) or baseline CD4 count (p>0.7).	models similar). No adjustment for multiple comparisons. Sex, age, baseline FFMI, alcohol, smoking, assets, smear+/-, trial arm, HIV
Van Lettow (2005) Van Lettow (2004) – subpopulation[87, 88]	Cross-sectional (TB diagnosis)	Malawi; urban, not stated IP/OP	1999–2000	500	All adults; smear+ PTB Mean age 31-36 Men 45% PLHIV 74%	HIV status Radiographic severity	Body cell mass / fat mass (BIA)	Lower BCM in men LHIV (41.0±3.8 vs 39.4±3.1 HIV-; p=0.001) but not women (33.6±3.2 vs 33.2±3.2; p=0.39) Lower body cell mass not associated with more severe radiographic disease after adjustment (adj p 0.51)	Age, sex, HIV (where indicated)
Villamor (2006)[85]	Cross-sectional (TB diagnosis)	Tanzania, urban outpatient TB clinics	2000–2004	731	All adults; smear+ Mean age: 35 Male: 69% PLHIV 32% (none on ART)	HIV status Sputum bacillary burden Functional severity (Karnofsky score) Socioeconomic status	Body cell mass Arm muscle circumference Phase angle	Trend towards lower AMC among people with fewer assets (diff -0.7; 95%CI 1.1, 0.2; p=0.06 for 0 assets vs 4-5 among men and 0.6; 1.2, 0.0; p=0.13 among women). Poorer physical function associated with lower AMC in both men and women (Karnofsky score <70 coeff -1.5; -1.9, -1.2; p<0.0001 in men and -1.6; -2.0, -1.2; p<0.0001 in women) No association between bacillary burden and AMC (p=0.55 for men and p=0.13 for women) Lower AMC among PLHIV (adj diff -0.3; -0.6, 0.0; p=0.02 for men and -0.3; -0.7, 0.0; p=0.05 for women) – additionally adjusted for Karnofsky score and bacillary burden	Adjusted for HIV, age, education, married, markers of socio-economic status
Huang (2025)[37]	Retrospective cohort (TB diagnosis)	China, urban, not stated IP/OP	2020–2023	309	Bact+ DS pTB Median age 43; Men 70% HIV/diabetes excluded	Age Sex Smoking Alcohol Radiographic severity	CT-measured muscle mass (T12 SMI)	Low T12 SMI associated with older age (median 52 vs 41 among those with normal SMI (p=0.035); being male (32% vs 11% women low SMI; p<0.001) Radiographic extent associated with low SMI including presence of cavities (41% vs 19% without cavities; p<0.001) and other markers; these associations persisted after adjustment for age, sex, muscle density. No association with alcohol and smoking	None, other than where indicated.

Abbreviations: Adj, adjusted; ACT, α1-antichymotrypsin; AGE, advanced glycation end products; AMC/MAMC, (mid-)arm muscle circumference; AMA, arm muscle area; ART, antiretroviral therapy; BCM, body cell mass; BIA, bioelectrical impedance analysis; BMI, body mass index; CD4, CD4+ T-cell count; CI, confidence interval; CT, computed tomography; DEXA/DXA, dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry; DS-TB, drug-susceptible tuberculosis; D₂O, deuterium (heavy-water) dilution; FFMI (FFM-I), fat-free mass index; Hb, haemoglobin; MDR-TB, multidrug-resistant tuberculosis; MWU, Mann Whitney U test; OR, odds ratio; pTB, pulmonary tuberculosis; PLHIV, people living with HIV; PM, protein mass; PMI, pectoralis muscle index; p-ratio, proportion of energy stored as protein; RCT, randomised controlled trial; SES/SEP, socioeconomic status/position; SMI, skeletal muscle index; sRAGE, soluble receptor for advanced glycation end products; TB, tuberculosis; CML, Nε-(carboxymethyl)lysine. *Units (where applicable):* BMI kg/m²; CD4 cells/μL; Hb g/dL; AMA cm²; AMC/MAMC cm; Grip strength kg; BCM kg; FFMI/LMI kg/m²; SMI/PMI cm²/m²; sRAGE pg/mL; CML assay-dependent (report as per study); Where stated, %ART is the % of people with HIV.;

* Praygod (2015) reports follow up of a subset of 116 people included in Praygod (2013)

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1067 **Supplementary Figure 1: Cumulative publications over time**

Included skeletal-muscle TB studies vs. all TB (MeSH) publications in 1,000s

Notes: One line shows the studies we included in our TB and skeletal muscle scoping review.
The other shows all records identified from a PubMed MeSH "Tuberculosis" search]
(overall values are in thousands in the source export)

Data: PubMed exports for cumulative TB studies.

1068 **Supplementary Figure 2: Muscle measures reported in included studies:**

Muscle Measurement Methods Across Included Primary Studies

60 measurements across 42 studies with any muscle measure

Note: *Performance tests include Chair stand assessment n=3

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1070 **Supplementary Figure 3: Measures derived from anthropometric measurements in included**
1071 **studies:**

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